

UNIVERSITÀ
DEGLI STUDI DELLA
TUSCIA

Master's degree in

Security and Human Rights - LM90

**Status of citizen, migrant and labour law:
non-discrimination in the labour market**

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ACADEMIC YEAR 2024/2025

Abbreviations

EU - The European Union

OECD - The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development

AMIF - Asylum, migration and integration fund

ESF+ - The European Social Fund Plus

CFREU - The Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union

CJEU - The Court of Justice of the European Union

NGO - Non-governmental organization

TCNs - third-country nationals

ENAR - European Network Against Racism

ILO - The International Labour Organization

AGG - the General Equal Treatment Act

LTRD – The Long-term Residents Directive

RD – Royal Decree

TIE - Tarjeta de Identidad de Extranjero (Foreigner's Identification Card)

CEDRE - The Council for the Elimination of Racial or Ethnic Discrimination

OBERAXE - The Government's Observatory on Racism and Xenophobia

ERDF - The European Regional Development Fund

EPI - The Economic Policy Institute

EIN - The Employer Identification Number

SEPE - The Public State Employment Service

CSOs - Civil society organisations

FRA - EU Agency for Fundamental Rights

PICUM - Platform for International Cooperation on Undocumented Migrants

Abstract

This master's thesis examines the status of citizens and migrants in the European Union (EU) with particular emphasis on non-discrimination in the labour market. The paper focuses on how citizenship and legal status influence access to employment and equal treatment across member states. It also highlights the dual nature of migration into the EU, both through regular and irregular channels, and the challenges this creates for labour integration. The central legal guarantees protecting the rights of migrants are derived from the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (CFREU), alongside the Racial Equality Directive and the Employment Equality Directive, which establish the principle of equality and the prohibition of discrimination.

The research also analyses the role of the institutions, as well as civil society organisations, in promoting and safeguarding migrants' rights. Special attention is given to Spain as a case study, examining its national strategies, local initiatives, and collaborations with NGOs in integrating migrants into the labour market. The thesis identifies key issues such as unequal treatment, barriers to labour market entry for irregular or recently arrived migrants, and persistent structural discrimination and describes the Spanish anti-discrimination law.

In addition, the thesis discusses gender-related problems, particularly the situation of migrant women, who often face double discrimination and wage inequality. Their social and economic vulnerabilities are considered within the broader context of EU and national labour market policies.

Based on EU legislation, Spanish practice, and real-life examples, the study aims to evaluate how effectively the principles of equality and non-discrimination are implemented in the European labour market. Ultimately, it seeks to determine whether a level playing field truly exists between EU nationals and non-EU nationals, and to suggest legal and policy recommendations for stronger protection and inclusion.

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Introduction

“If people have the opportunity for a decent job, education, healthcare, and security, I believe forced migration will be eliminated.” – Nayib Bukele

Migration, a long-standing aspect of human history, has been driven by conflict, poverty, persecution, and the pursuit of better opportunities. In the 21st century, however, migration has become a contentious issue in Europe, particularly within the European Union (EU). For many migrants, Europe offers safety and the prospect of a dignified life, yet integration into EU societies remains challenging.

Migrants and asylum seekers face barriers at borders, in administrative procedures, and in their daily lives. Access to the labour market stands out as a significant obstacle. Employment is not just a source of livelihood but also a pathway to independence, integration, and equal participation in society. The EU has enshrined basic rights through the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (CFREU) and directives like the Racial Equality Directive and the Employment Equality Directive¹. These legal instruments prohibit discrimination and guarantee fair working conditions. However, despite these formal guarantees, migrants often experience unequal protection compared to EU citizens. Their employment prospects are shaped by complex factors, including legal status, qualification recognition, language barriers, social prejudice, and bureaucratic fragmentation. Migrant women, in particular, face multiple and/or intersectional discrimination. based on gender and migration status, making their integration even more difficult.

Against this backdrop, the central research question of this thesis is to explore the non-discrimination and labour rights of migrants in the EU compared to those of EU citizens, and to examine whether these rights are effectively protected in practice. To answer this question, the thesis aims to achieve four main objectives: **first**, it aims to explore the legal and theoretical foundations of citizenship, migration, and labour rights within the EU. **Second**, It will examine how non-discrimination rules are implemented at both EU and national levels. **Third**, to investigate the role of institutions, Non Governmental Organisations (NGOs), and civil society in promoting

¹ Council Directive 2000/78/EC of 27 November 2000 establishing a general framework for equal treatment in employment and occupation

equal access to the labour market. **Fourth**, identify existing gaps in protection, proposing recommendations for stronger and more effective measures.

As for the structure of the thesis, it consists of three chapters:

Chapter 1 introduces the legal and theoretical framework, explaining concepts such as citizenship/denizenship, migration status, and demonstrating how they intersect in EU law. Building on this foundation, **chapter 2** delves into the EU's legal framework on non-discrimination, focussing on the CFREU, the Equality Directives, and some relevant case law of the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU). Moving from the broader EU level to a concrete national context, **chapter 3** shifts to practice, analysing Spain's integration system, its fragmented legal and administrative frameworks, and the persistent barriers that migrants face And the advanced antidiscrimination law. It also explores the role of NGOs and civil society as mediators and advocates, as well as the policy gaps that continue to undermine equal treatment.

Taken together, these chapters highlight a paradox: **while migrants in the EU, particularly in Spain, enjoy rights on paper, their practical realisation remains limited. This gap between law and practice underscores the need for robust enforcement, streamlined administrative procedures, accessible funding, and the active inclusion of migrant-led organisations.**

Ultimately, the thesis argues that ensuring equal labour rights and combating discrimination is not only a legal requirement but also a social and economic necessity. Protecting migrants' labour rights contributes to human dignity, strengthens integration, and fosters fairer and more cohesive societies across the EU.

Chapter I

Being Migrants: Migrant Status Differences vs. Citizens

1.1 Theoretical Concepts: Citizenship, Migrant Status, and Intersection with Work

To understand the intersection between citizenship and migrant status in relation to employment access and rights, it's crucial to clarify the conceptual and legal differences between these two categories. This involves determining what constitutes migrants, identifying the challenges they face, and exploring potential gaps in legislation and policy with the view to suggest improvements.

To achieve this, it is necessary to define the meaning of citizenship and migrant status within the legal systems. This requires understanding the types of citizenship and migrant statuses that exist along with their respective advantages and disadvantages. However, this subchapter focuses on national citizenship and the status of legally residing migrants within the EU, particularly those who may encounter discrimination in the labour market.

Migrants are particularly vulnerable to multiple forms of discrimination, both direct and indirect, in access to employment, housing, health, education, and social services. Institutional and/or structural discrimination refers to rules, norms, routines, patterns of attitudes, and behaviour in institutions and other societal structures that represent obstacles to groups or individuals in achieving the same rights and opportunities as the majority population.

As argued in *Structural Injustice and Workers' Rights* (2023), such barriers exemplify Iris Marion Young's theory of structural injustice. **Young contends that individuals' rights are undermined not by isolated acts but by the cumulative effect of institutions and practices that appear neutral yet perpetuate inequality.**² This discrimination can be either open or hidden and may occur intentionally or unintentionally. The result is that patterns of interaction among groups within society exclude identified groups or individuals based on concrete traits.³

² Mantouvalou, V. (2023). *Structural Injustice and Workers' Rights*. Oxford University Press. pp 5-6

³ Taran, P., & Gächter, A. (2015). *Discrimination against Migrant Workers Global Trends, Responses, Challenges and Ways Forward Today and Tomorrow*. CERD Geneva.

As highlighted in “As Equal as Others”, **formalequality alone is insufficient. Substantive equality demands proactive state action to eliminate structural barriers and guarantee genuine access to work and social protection.**⁴

Before turning to theoretical debates, it is useful to recall that international law has long defined discrimination in employment. The International Labour Organization (ILO) Convention No. 111 (1958) and the UN Convention on Migrant Workers (1990) describe discrimination as direct, indirect, and in some cases allow for positive measures. These global norms reinforce EU anti-discrimination law and clarify that even neutral practices may disproportionately disadvantage migrants.⁵

The fundamental legal and social difference between citizens and migrants is crucial to the organisation of modern nation-states. Citizenship, in addition to being a legal status, is a symbolic institution that grants individuals full rights and obligations, civil, political, or social. It defines the relationship between the state and its citizens and marks national identity and belonging. Citizenship denotes formal membership in a nation-state.⁶ Citizenship is a legal status that grants individuals specific rights and responsibilities as members of the political community that forms the nation-state’s demographic basis. It also symbolises membership in the nation (Joppke, 2007).⁷ The 1992 Maastricht Treaty introduced the concept of EU citizenship, creating a shared identity among nationals of EU Member States. However, EU citizenship is only granted to nationals of EU countries, leaving non-EU nationals, often referred to as third-country nationals, who reside in EU Member States, excluded from its rights and privileges. As the CJEU has consistently emphasised, EU citizenship is the fundamental status of nationals of the Member States. However, its scope remains limited. Case law confirms that third-country nationals cannot directly invoke EU citizenship rights unless secondary legislation grants them derivative rights.⁸ This legal and social divide within the EU persists based on nationality and migratory status.

⁴ Jenoff, P. (2013). As Equal as Others? Rethinking Access to Discrimination Law. *University of Cincinnati Law Review*, 81(1), 85-126. pp 94-95

⁵ Gächter, A. (2022). Migrant workers and discrimination: realities, threats, and remedies. *Revista Tecnológica-ESPOL*, 34(1), 92-112. , pp 100-102

⁶Joppke C, Transformation of Citizenship: Status, Rights, Identity, *Citizenship Studies* 11(1), 2007, pp. 37–48.

⁷ Bivand Erdal, M., & Midtbøen, A. H. (2023). ‘Birthplace unknown’: on the symbolic value of the passport for identity-construction among naturalised citizens. *Identities*, 30(1), 19-37.

⁸ European Commission: Directorate-General for Justice, European Network of Legal Experts in the Non-Discrimination Field & O’Cinneide, C. (2013). The evolution and impact of the case-law of the Court of Justice of the

On the other hand, some literature argues that citizenship can be understood from an international perspective as a sorting device for allocating human populations to sovereign states. According to Bauböck, under international understanding the relationship between states and their citizens is a legal bond that must be respected by other states. This bond entails certain duties between states, such as the obligation to readmit a person to the state whose citizen they are. International law also supports the right of states to determine, under their domestic law, who their citizens are.⁹

There are different theories about citizenship. There are different theories about citizenship and examining all of them lies beyond the scope of this thesis. In the aftermath of the Second World War, T.H. Marshall's influential account (1950) conceptualized citizenship as a single package of civil, political, and social rights. He argued that British citizenship evolved over centuries, with "social citizenship" (including welfare and labor protections) being added to political and civil rights by the 20th century.¹⁰ According to Marshall's theory, national citizenship implies a claim to decent work and social support. In more recent times, Rogers Brubaker explores how nation-states define citizenship through myths and law.¹¹ He demonstrates that France and Germany, for instance, historically had vastly different perceptions of "the nation", leading to contrasting citizenship policies - birthright versus bloodline. Brubaker emphasizes that citizenship often serves to include some while excluding others, profoundly shaping migrants' status.¹² According to the US sociologist, citizenship is a constructed boundary between "insiders" and "outsiders", which often marginalises migrants and casts them outside the full community of rights.

Scholars like Rainer Bauböck examine transnational and post-national citizenship, exploring how globalisation transforms it. Bauböck discusses how migrants can hold multiple loyalties, including dual or multiple citizenships, challenging the notion that one must renounce their origin ties.¹³ Joseph Carens¹⁴, a liberal egalitarian, argues that citizenship in the modern

European Union on Directives 2000/43/EC and 2000/78/EC, Publications Office. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2838/38584>, pp 14-15

⁹ Bauböck, R. (2006). *Migration and citizenship: legal status, rights and political participation*. Amsterdam University Press, p 16

¹⁰ Ibid, p 23

¹¹ Brubaker R., the publication of Rogers Brubaker's seminal study on citizenship policy in Germany and France

¹² Bauböck, R. (2006). *Migration and citizenship: cit.*, p. 40.

¹³ Ibid pp 28-29

¹⁴ Carens, J. H. (1992), 'Migration and Morality. A Liberal Egalitarian Perspective', in B. Barry & R. E. Goodin (eds.), *Free Movement. Ethical Issues in the transnational migration of people and of money*, 25-47.

world is a lot like feudal status in the medieval world. It is assigned at birth; for the most part it is not subject to change by the individual's will and efforts; and it has a major impact upon that person's life chances.¹⁵

Complementing these perspectives, status-based approaches highlight intermediate categories that exist between citizens and non-citizens. Sociologists and critical theorists use terms such as denizen, precarity, and neoliberal citizenship to describe these groups. For example, John Lea describes the precariat and denizen as labour-status groups lacking full rights. Precariat refers to the growth of a social stratum within the working class characterized by job insecurity, short term contracts, lack of rights at work and often low pay. The denizen, in contrast to the citizen, is characterised by effective dispossession of rights, including protection from crime, social welfare, political rights, and the representation of interests. This combination describes what has been happening at the bottom of the labour market during the worst recession since the 1930s. The term 'precariat' implies a combination of both precariousness and dispossession.¹⁶

The precariat refers to workers in unstable, low-wage jobs with no clear status. In contrast, denizens are long-term residents who have some protections, such as work permits, but remain excluded from political rights and many social benefits. As John Lea notes, denizens are characterised by effective dispossession of rights, including welfare, political voice, and equal protection, unlike citizens. This reflects a neoliberal vision of citizenship, where states marketise welfare and intentionally stratify rights. Migrants often fall into these categories, holding limited work visas (denizens) and facing precarious labour conditions without the full safety net afforded to citizens. Brubaker and others emphasise that citizenship is a constructed boundary between "insiders" and "outsiders," which often marginalises migrants and casts them outside the full community of rights. In response, concepts like denizenship highlight that some long-term migrants acquire partial rights, such as economic, social rights, yet remain in an "in-between" status between alien and citizen.¹⁷ The status of denizen, which is being granted increasingly often to third-country nationals in Europe, has been formed as the result of long historical processes.¹⁸

¹⁵ Ibid p 16

¹⁶ Lea, J. (2013). From denizen to citizen and back: Governing the Precariat through crime: John Lea explains the processes behind (re) creating precariousness and dispossession. *Criminal Justice Matters*, 93(1), 4-5.

¹⁷ Łucka, D. (2019). Between Alien and Citizen: Denizenship in the "Old" and "New" Europe. *Polish Sociological Review*, 207(3), 337-354. p 337

¹⁸ Ibid. p 340

At the same time, neoliberal citizenship theory¹⁹ argues that based on rationalities of value that “challenge classic dichotomies between inside/outside, inclusion/exclusion, members/strangers”. The rationalities of value underlying neoliberal citizenship exclude, dispose or sacrifice those without value or with low-value for the labour market, those whose work can be done at cheaper cost by others, those who need welfare provision to live a life in dignity, and also those whose presence does not contribute to the emotional welfare of a country and its population. In both free movement within the EU and immigration to the EU these rationalities are incorporated in the application of seemingly neutral legal and policy concepts such as ‘sufficient financial resources’, ‘worker’, ‘partnership’ or ‘talent’ that condition access to territory, welfare and residence rights.²⁰ This framework explains how formally neutral rules, such as requiring a “worker” visa or “sufficient resources,” systematically disadvantage certain migrants in practice. In Europe, these theories intersect with labour market segmentation, channelling migrants into secondary sectors with low wages and limited mobility. Consequently, formal citizenship rights remain out of reach, resulting in a precarity that is both legal and socio-economic.

Classical dual-labour-market theory, proposed by Piore and Doeringer²¹, suggests a primary segment of stable, well-paid jobs and a secondary segment of low-paying, precarious jobs. Migrants disproportionately inhabit the secondary segment, and informal work, which includes undeclared and unprotected labour, is another tier often occupied by undocumented migrants. Under restrictive immigration regimes, a tiered system emerges, with high-skilled migrants having comparatively strong rights, while temporary or irregular migrants have few.²²

Feminist and postcolonial approaches highlight how migration and work are gendered, racialised, and shaped by global inequality.²³ Migrant women frequently face a “double disadvantage” due to both gender and migrant status.²⁴ In essence, these critical perspectives reveal that citizenship and work are never gender- or race-neutral. Policies and practices may privilege

¹⁹ Mavelli, L. (2018). Citizenship for sale and the neoliberal political economy of belonging. *International Studies Quarterly*, 62(3), 482-493. p 491

²⁰ Schrauwen, A. (2024). Essential, invisible, discriminated and exchangeable: labour migrants in the EU. *Transnational Legal Theory*, 15 (4), 572-590. p 575

²¹ Doeringer, P. and Piore, M. (1971) *Internal Labour Markets and Manpower Analysis*.

²² Leontaridi, M. (1998). Segmented labour markets: theory and evidence. *Journal of economic surveys*, 12(1), 103-109. p 70-73

²³ Schiek, D. (2018). On uses, mis-uses and non-uses of intersectionality before the Court of Justice (EU). *International Journal of Discrimination and the Law*, 18(2-3), 82-103.

²⁴ OECD. (2023). *International Migration Outlook 2024*. OECD Publishing. p 4

certain migrants, such as male workers with degrees, while disadvantaging others, like undocumented women of colour in care jobs.

These theoretical frameworks are relevant to the EU context, as it offers a unique form of citizenship and freedom of movement to its nationals. Directive 2004/38²⁵, ensures that EU nationals can move to and work in another member country without discrimination.²⁶ Article 45 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union²⁷ explicitly prohibits nationality-based discrimination in employment and working conditions for EU citizens. Citizenship is a mechanism that draws boundaries between those fully included in the labour market and society, and those who remain on the margins. This process is ongoing.

This novel concept of integration²⁸, assuming a role formerly played by nationality laws, chiefly as a condition for naturalisation²⁹The term ‘civic’ emphasises the level of integration required from TCNs to attain legal status, i.e., citizenship. The functional aspects of integration, associated with a civic (citizenship) status, have been transferred from nationality per se to immigration as a fundamental condition for regularity and access to rights and freedoms for TCNs. Immigrants are portrayed as ‘abnormal individuals’ in need of a process of normalisation or naturalisation into the envisioned canon of ‘life and identity’. Differences and complexities are presented as being and being perceived as transcending the normality of life and the nation. Although TCNs may not desire to renounce their national identities and ‘naturalise’ into the ideal citizen, the state compels allegiance to a set of perceived values, customs, and principles.³⁰ To legally reside in any state, according to the state national administrative law, Temporary Community Residents must demonstrate compliance with the previously applied juridical conditions, which were solely requirements for those seeking national citizenship. These conditions have now become central to obtaining a regular status of residence. When assessing the

²⁵ Directive 2004/38/EC on the right of citizens of the Union and their family members to move and reside freely within the territory of the Member States

²⁶ <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/factsheets/en/sheet/41/free-movement-of-workers#:~:text=within%20the%20European%20single%20market,on%20afterwards%20under%20certain%20conditions>

²⁷ Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union, art 45

²⁸ Carrera, S., & Wiesbrock, A. (2009). *Civic Integration of Third Country Nationals: Nationalism versus Europeanisation in the Common EU Immigration Policy*.

²⁹ Bauböck, R., Ersbøll, E., Groenendijk, K., & Waldrauch, H. (Eds.). (2006). *Acquisition and loss of nationality: Comparative analyses-policies and trends in 15 European countries* (Vol. 1). Amsterdam University Press.

³⁰ Carrera, S., & Wiesbrock, A. (2009). *Civic Integration of Third Country Nationals: Nationalism versus Europeanisation in the Common EU Immigration Policy*. p 3

integration of immigrants in immigration law by EU member states, it becomes evident that there are both internal and external dimensions. The internal dimension encompasses programmes, courses, tests, or contracts that TCNs must complete upon entering a state's territory and seeking legal residence. Civic integration is applied to newcomers, those applying for permanent residence, and in the context of family reunification. It often serves as a condition or additional layer for holding a temporary residence permit or being granted permanent residence, thereby providing greater security against expulsion. For TCNs, this internal dimension necessitates their passing of a programme or exam (or both) covering history, institutions, and values (symbols) to avoid precarious and insecure residence status. The primary focus of the internal dimension is on access to social protection and the security of residence. One of the most significant sanctions for failing integration tests is the non-renewal of a temporary residence permit, resulting in expulsion from the country.

The external dimension ³¹encompasses evaluations and courses administered by the consular and diplomatic authorities of European Union (EU) member states in non-EU countries. These evaluations assess the lifestyle and values of the nation-state involved. Integration is being externalised, with the state's requirement for individual integration extending beyond its territorial boundaries towards the country of origin. The civic integration test serves as an additional immigration control and selection measure, "at a distance," ³²demonstrating its full managerial impact even before individuals are permitted to move and enter the destination country. Consequently, they are formally classified as immigrants under the national immigration law of the destination country. The external dimension emphasises access to territory and reducing the number of entries based on family reunification. For potential migrants, civic integration abroad is another discretionary condition for obtaining a visa and the right to move to EU territory. As discussed later, this dimension raises fundamental human rights implications. Integration is presented as an additional criterion on the path towards legality and the entitlement to claim rights, security, and protection, both internally and externally. It functions as an additional rule for the state to manage, limit, and select the regular channels of migration and the community of beneficiaries entitled to social security and social solidarity. Consequently, access to rights and the

³¹ Ibid p 4

³² Bigo, D., & Guild, E. (2005) (eds), *Controlling Frontiers*, Aldershot: Ashgate, 2005; see also D Bigo, D., & Guild, E. (2005), *La Mise à L'Écart des Étrangers: La Logique du Visa Schengen*, Cultures & Conflits, Paris: L'Harmattan, 2003.

politics of identity are closely intertwined by the state's immigration policy. This link necessitates the Temporary Community (TCN) to adhere to national identity, encompassing the perceived lifestyle, values, symbols, and traditions of the nation. Integration is not viewed as a process of social inclusion and equalisation of rights and freedoms, but rather as a state requirement for the TCN to assimilate into the homogenous national wholeness. This approach functions as a means for the state to promote national identity and nationalism both within and beyond its territorial boundaries. In this context, civic integration and the respect for diversity become mutually exclusive concepts. This opposition to diversity challenges the principles upon which liberal democracies within the European Union (EU) and the EU itself are founded. This version of integration is incompatible with a rights-based approach to migration. Furthermore, it undermines social inclusion by promoting social exclusion and exacerbating the vulnerability and insecurity of individuals on the move and those non-EU nationals already residing within the Union.³³

The European Union institutionalized this difference. The Maastricht Treaty of 1992 introduced the concept of EU citizenship, which granting every national of a member state the rights to free move, reside, work across the EU.³⁴ As a result, the legal framework applies to EU nationals, except for third-country nationals (TCNs), who are individuals from non-EU states residing within the EU. TCNs are excluded from many of the associated rights. While some TCNs may gain access to long-term residence status under Directive 2003/109/EC³⁵, they are still excluded from EU citizenship, its associated political rights and free movement. While EU citizenship remains strictly tied to nationality of a Member State, as noted by Schiffner³⁶ the EU has gradually developed a form of "European denizenship" for long-term third-country residents. This status, granted by litigation before the CJEU³⁷ and by the CFREU, extends many citizenship-related rights to TCNs, particularly those holding long-term residence status under Directive 2003/109/EC.³⁸ This status provides equal treatment with nationals in areas such as employment, education, social security, and even limited free movement across Member States. Scholars

³³ Carrera, S., & Wiesbrock, A. (2009). Civic Integration of Third Country Nationals: Nationalism versus Europeanisation in the Common EU Immigration Policy. p 3-5

³⁴ Treaty on European Union (Maastricht Treaty), OJ C 191, 29.7.1992.

³⁵ Council Directive 2003/109/EC of 25 November 2003 concerning the status of third-country nationals who are long-term residents, OJ L 16, 23.1.2004.

³⁶ Schiffner, I. (2018). Denizenship - A New Fundamental Status in the EU? *Marmara Journal of European Studies*, 26(2), 69-82. p 69

³⁷ Rhimou Chakroun v. Minister van Buitenlandse Zaken, 2010

³⁸ Ibid p 69-77

describe this as a quasi-citizenship or “partial membership,” bridging the gap between full EU citizenship and migrant exclusion³⁹ As a result, a new legal category has emerged in scholarly and policy discourse denizenship. In modern democracies, the concept of denizenship highlights the fragmentation of rights. Legal residence doesn’t always translate into equal treatment, particularly in the labour market. This structural basis for discrimination reinforces inequalities between citizens and migrants.

The intersection between legal status whether citizenship, denizen ship or migrant categories and access to work is particularly critical in shaping socio-economic inclusion. In most legal systems, citizenship guarantees unrestricted access to the national labor market, including the full range of employment protections, union membership, and access to public benefits. Conversely, migrants' access to employment is often regulated by their residency status, work permits, or sector-specific authorizations, which may limit job mobility and increase dependency on employers.⁴⁰ Migrant workers, particularly those with temporary or irregular status, are disproportionately represented in low-wage, precarious, and often informal sectors, such as agriculture, domestic work, and construction.⁴¹ While anti-discrimination protections are formally in place under both national and EU law, they are often inadequately enforced and fail to reach vulnerable migrant populations, particularly those with undocumented or short-term legal status.⁴² There are rulings concerning discrimination, for instance in recent times , the CJEU referred Italy and Germany : The European Commission referred Italy to the Court of Justice of the European Union for discriminating against mobile EU workers regarding family benefits. Italy’s new family allowance scheme, which requires two years of residency for eligibility, violates EU law on social security coordination and the free movement of workers. The Commission argues that EU mobile workers should receive the same family benefits as local workers, regardless of their residency status. In Germany , The European Commission referred Germany to the Court of Justice of the European Union for discriminating against mobile EU workers regarding family benefits. Bavaria’s scheme, which reduced benefits for EU nationals with children residing in lower-cost

³⁹ Ibid p 75-80

⁴⁰ Costello C.(2016), *The Human Rights of Migrants and Refugees in European Law*, Oxford University Press, pp. 121–134.

⁴¹ European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights (FRA)(2019), *Protecting Migrant Workers from Exploitation in the EU: Workers’ Perspectives*, Available at: <https://fra.europa.eu>.

⁴² FRA, *Second European Union Minorities and Discrimination Survey (2017) Main Results*

Member States, violates EU law on social security coordination and the free movement of workers. The Commission argues that EU mobile workers should receive the same benefits as local workers.

So, in conclusion employment is not a matter of economic participation, otherwise it is site where broader issues of legal recognition, inclusion, and social justice are negotiated, the labour market becomes a key arena in which the differences between citizens and migrants are both produced and reinforced. This is not only through law, but also through institutional practices and social perceptions. Migrant status often means occupying an intermediate or marginal position within this regime, characterised by legal precariousness and social vulnerability. Feminist and postcolonial approaches remind us that these positions are also shaped by gender, race, and history. In the EU, this results in a complex interplay of full EU citizens, second-class EU citizens (e.g., very recent arrivals under entry conditions)⁴³, long-term residents, temporary workers, and irregular migrants, each group facing varying access to jobs, labour rights, and inclusion.

To sum up as for migrants' problems in Intersection process with Work, there are different main issues that have to be important for this thesis are Ethnic and Racial Discrimination in the Labor Market, Institutional Barriers and Bureaucratic Exclusion and Gender and Intersectional Disadvantage.

Racialised migrants in the EU face pervasive biases throughout their employment journey. These biases manifest in hiring and recruitment, where candidates may be screened based on name, address, or appearance. Employers may favour candidates with “native-sounding” names or local addresses, and some even request photos to exclude visible minorities.⁴⁴ EU directives require all member states to implement mechanisms for equality in employment, including access and prohibit various forms of discrimination.⁴⁵ Common consequences of racial inequality in the labour market are unemployment, barriers to work, direct and indirect discrimination. Discrimination against minorities is most evident in recruitment, where they face multiple barriers to entering the labour market in countries such as Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, the Netherlands, Finland, Germany, Greece, Ireland, and Norway.⁴⁶ Despite laws against discrimination in

⁴³ Lamberts, M., Ode, A., & Witcamp, B. (2014). Racism and discrimination in employment in Europe: ENAR Shadow Report. Brussels: ENAR. p 32

⁴⁴ Ibid p 3

⁴⁵ Race Equality Directive 2000/43/EC, Directive 2000/78/EC, Directive 2006/54/EC, Directive Proposal COM(2008) 462. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:52014DC0002>, art 1

⁴⁶ Michael L., Reynolds D. (2022) racial discrimination racial discrimination in Europe: ENAR Shadow Report. Brussels: ENAR, p 6

recruitment, job advertisements often actively discourage certain groups from applying. This can be done directly by requiring specific documents or language requirements, or indirectly by implying that certain groups are less suitable. Employers can also justify discrimination as a “better candidate,” but studies have shown that CVs with non-European sounding names are less likely to receive an interview, even if they contain similar content. As a result of this, highly educated migrants report being discriminated against when applying for jobs, despite their strong language skills and other resources. This finding aligns with *As Equal as Others*, which emphasises how systemic exclusion in employment, housing, and healthcare perpetuates cycles of disadvantage for migrants.⁴⁷ In Portugal, migrants face poorer career prospects than nationals, with lower wages, fewer promotion prospects, unfavourable working conditions, and frequent verbal or physical harassment.⁴⁸ Discrimination in the workplace is a common experience across the EU. In Lithuania, the Office of the Equal Opportunities Ombudsperson receives the most complaints related to workplace discrimination. Between 2019 and 2020, in France, out of the 4% of racist discrimination cases registered by the police, two-thirds were related to the professional sphere.⁴⁹ Sweden experienced some of the highest increases in reporting during this period, doubling between 2017 and 2020⁵⁰. However, significant levels of under-reporting remain. Litigation levels are low among racialised groups, particularly migrants, who are fearful of losing their residence or work permits.⁵¹ Once employed, racialised workers systematically occupy the bottom of the hierarchy. Studies across Europe show that “migrants and ethnic minorities tend to have jobs further down the hierarchy and lower wages” compared to locals. This is particularly evident in Denmark, the United Kingdom, and Spain, where high rates of overqualification among immigrants and ethnic minorities are observed. Consequently, they are underrepresented in management positions, making it challenging for many to utilise their education in high-quality

⁴⁷ Jenoff, P. (2013). *As Equal as Others? Rethinking Access to Discrimination Law*. University of Cincinnati Law Review, 81(1), 85-126. pp 97-98

⁴⁸ Michael L., Reynolds D. (2022) racial discrimination in europe : ENAR Shadow Report. Brussels: ENAR , p 21

⁴⁹ France, country report.

⁵⁰ DO, Diskrimineringsombudsmannen, Rapport 2021:1, Statistik 2015-2020, Statistik över anmälningar, tips och klagomål som inkommit till Diskrimineringsombudsmannen åren 2015-2020, s. 35. “Antalet anmälningar, tips och klagomål om diskriminering inom arbetslivet som har samband med etnisk tillhörighet respektive kön är vanligast”

⁵¹ Ibid p 22

jobs. Migrants are underrepresented in management and professional roles while concentrated in low-skill sectors such as hospitality, transport, or cleaning.⁵²

Migrant disadvantage is reinforced by legal and administrative frameworks that impose hidden restrictions. Many EU laws and national rules explicitly differentiate between citizens and non-citizens, or among migrant categories. For instance, qualified migrants often find their foreign diplomas unrecognised, necessitating expensive and time-consuming re-qualification. ENAR highlights the problematic procedure of recognising foreign qualifications as a significant obstacle.⁵³ ⁵⁴Employers and regulators may legally restrict hiring non-nationals, giving priority to EU citizens or even excluding entire groups. Shadow reports document that many Member States deny asylum-seekers any right to work. For example, in Ireland and Germany, asylum applicants must wait up to ten years before they can gain legal employment.⁵⁵

At a higher level, the patchwork of EU migration laws creates a fragmented rights regime. Unlike citizens, most migrants lack a blanket guarantee of equal treatment under primary EU law. This has resulted in a “fragmented legal framework” for third-country nationals’ social rights, with entitlements tied to narrow secondary directives rather than universal guarantees, as one analysis observes.⁵⁶ By limiting the scope of Article 21(2) of the Charter of Fundamental Rights⁵⁷ to EU citizens, the Court emphasises that EU citizenship is a privileged status intrinsically linked to Member States and their nationals. This ensures that the legal framework prioritises the rights and obligations of EU citizens over those of third-country nationals (TCNs). This approach reflects the institutional and political objectives of EU law, which aim to strike a balance between fostering inclusivity and preserving Member State sovereignty in areas such as immigration and the treatment of TCNs. However, this approach has resulted in a fragmented legal framework for protecting the rights of TCNs, leaving their entitlements heavily reliant on secondary legislation

⁵² ENAR European Network Against Racism. (2017). *Racism & Discrimination in Employment in Europe 2013–2017.*, p 4

⁵³ Lamberts, M., Ode, A., & Witcamp, B. (2014). *Racism and discrimination in employment in Europe: ENAR Shadow Report.* Brussels: ENAR. p 3

⁵⁴ Michael L., Reynolds D. (2022) *Racial discrimination in Europe : ENAR Shadow Report.* Brussels: ENAR p 22

⁵⁵ ENAR European Network Against Racism. (2017). *Racism & Discrimination in Employment in Europe 2013–2017.*, p 31

⁵⁶ Manfredi, M. (2025). *Access to Social Benefits for Third-country Nationals in the European Union Between Fragmentation and Equal Treatment.* *European Papers-A Journal on Law and Integration*, 2025(1), 191-218, p 193

⁵⁷ Charter of fundamental rights of the European Union, art 21(2)

rather than enjoying the same guarantees provided to EU citizens under primary law.⁵⁸ In practice, migrants' welfare and services depend on the type and duration of their residence permit. Member States often use residency requirements to limit benefits, for example, many immigrants only become eligible for unemployment or housing aid after long legal residence. EU case law shows that nations regularly impose minimum-stay conditions before migrants can claim basic assistance, effectively excluding many newcomers. Other administrative barriers include large language or civic test requirements for social programmes and bureaucratic complexity that deters applications. Bureaucracy and policy create opaque immigration procedures and frequent status changes, such as transitioning from a student visa to a worker visa or temporary protection. This makes it difficult for migrants to navigate the system. Asylum-seekers, undocumented migrants, and even some legal residents often fall through the cracks of overlapping regulations, particularly regarding welfare exclusion. By EU law, only long-term residents eventually gain near-citizen benefit rights, as outlined in Directive 2003/109. Refugees and recent arrivals, however, may be explicitly barred from certain welfare programmes. This “by-status” differentiation means that two equally needy workers can receive very different support based solely on their immigration category.⁵⁹

When working together, institutional barriers create structural discrimination. This aligns with what *Structural Injustice and Workers' Rights* (2023) identifies as “background injustice”:⁶⁰ the systemic disadvantage embedded in labour market segmentation, where migrants are consistently pushed into precarious, low-protection jobs despite formal legal safeguards. The EU Anti-Racism Action Plan⁶¹ adopted in September 18, 2020, for the period of 2020-2025, recognizes the need for an intersectional approach to address structural racism, acknowledging its synergistic nature with other forms of discrimination. This disparity between the symbolic aspiration of EU law and its limited ability to transform power dynamics underscores the persistent exclusion of migrants, despite a robust legal framework. Structural racism, often unintentional, manifests in unequal outcomes for Black and minority ethnic groups and is characterized by historical, societal, and institutional elements. While individual discrimination is more visible,

⁵⁸ Thym, D. (2024). European Migration Law Between 'Rescuing' and 'Taming' the Nation State: A History of Half-hearted Commitment to Human Rights and Refugee Protection. *European Papers-A Journal on Law and Integration*, 2023(3), 1663-1678. pp 1663, 1667–1668.

⁵⁹ Manfredi, M. (2025). Access to Social Benefits for Third-country Nationals in the European Union Between Fragmentation and Equal Treatment. *European Papers-A Journal on Law and Integration*, 2025(1), 191 - 218, p 194

⁶⁰ Mantouvalou, V. (2023). *Structural Injustice and Workers' Rights*. Oxford University Press. , p 3

⁶¹ European Commission. (2020). A Union of equality: EU anti-racism action plan 2020–2025., p 2

structural discrimination perpetuates intergenerational inequality.⁶² During the structure discrimination process, migrants may legally be allowed to work or claim aid, but the restrictive conditions make it de facto exclusionary. As Mantouvalou emphasises, addressing this requires not only equal treatment laws but also redistributive and participatory remedies. These include empowering trade unions, ensuring collective bargaining coverage for migrant workers, and redesigning inspection systems to target structural inequalities. This cumulative effect means that legal status itself becomes a marker of worth. Only those deemed economically useful and fully integrated, such as high-skilled individuals or family members of citizens, enjoy expanded rights, while others remain stuck at the bottom by law.

Migrant women in Europe face a double or even triple disadvantage at the intersection of gender, ethnicity, and migrant status. They are often overrepresented in the most precarious, informal, and undervalued sectors, particularly domestic and care work, where labor protections are weakest. As one An Equinet EU report emphasizes, “the majority of caregivers in Europe are women, often migrant women in vulnerable situations.” Domestic and care work is culturally coded as “women’s work” and has traditionally been devalued⁶³. When combined with immigrant status, this creates an especially marginalised labor market sign. Migrant careworkers typically earn very low wages, work long hours without contracts, and lack normal social security. They also face heightened risks of abuse and exploitation, as highlighted by the Equinet study, which notes that care workers endure precarious contracts, language barriers, invisible qualifications, and even sexual harassment or violence on the job.⁶⁴

In the EU context, legal status, race, and gender intersect to shape labor outcomes.⁶⁵ Non-citizen workers, particularly migrant women, are relegated to a secondary labor market due to both formal rules and informal prejudices. This reality contradicts idealised citizenship theories, as even migrants with formal residency often face curtailed citizenship-like rights due to policy logic and social discrimination. Addressing these intertwined inequalities requires acknowledging that citizenship in practice is stratified. Migrant status mediates access to the rights theory promises,

⁶² Crowley, N. (2022). To name and address the underlying problem: Structural discrimination on the ground of racial or ethnic origin. Luxembourg: EU Publications Office. , introduction p. 40-42

⁶³ Schlenzka, N., Moana Genevey, Lite Mateo, A., Ortiz, B., & Equinet. (2021). *Domestic and care workers in Europe: an intersectional issue.* , p 14

⁶⁴ Ibid, p. 23

⁶⁵ Schiek, D. (2018). On uses, mis-uses and non-uses of intersectionality before the Court of Justice (EU). *International Journal of Discrimination and the Law*, 18(2-3), 82-103.

while ethnic/racial/gender biases add an additional layer of disadvantage. Experts' analyses, EU reports, and civil-society studies document how these dynamics play out across Member States. For instance, ENAR's shadow reports provide detailed national evidence of hiring bias and wage gaps. Academic work on neoliberal citizenship, such as Annette Schrauwen's work, helps explain the policy rationales that "sacrifice" vulnerable migrants.⁶⁶ In this framework, intersectionality help analysing.⁶⁷ Migrant women's labor experiences are compounded by discrimination. "Intersectionality", frequently used by political scientists, sociologists and anthropologists as a highly abstract concept, originated as the socio-legal critique. s regards EU law, some socio-legal scholars of today doubt that intersectionality has any value as a practically relevant concept. Briefly, intersectional discrimination can be characterized as discrimination on more than one ground where either the specific contribution of any one of these grounds is indiscernible or the full extent of discrimination is only recognizable by acknowledging the combination of two or more grounds.⁶⁸

These often female migrant workforces live in complex spaces where their labor, migration, and other legal regimes overlap. They work under precarious conditions, and in many cases, their legal status is insecure. Their vulnerability can only be understood from an intersectional perspective because their social position is influenced by the allocation of rights and resources based on their gender, race, class, nationality/citizenship, legal status, and language.⁶⁹ EU-level legal analyses finally reveal how permit-based exclusions undermine the freedom-to-work promised by EU law. These sources ground theoretical concepts in EU labour-market realities.

1.2 Migrants in the EU Labor Market: Data and Disparities

The European Union's labour market is characterised by increasing diversity, yet this diversity often leads to unequal access, treatment, and outcomes for migrants. While legal frameworks emphasise equality and non-discrimination, empirical data shows persistent

⁶⁶ Schrauwen, A. (2024). Essential, invisible, discriminated and exchangeable: labour migrants in the EU, p 575

⁶⁷ Crenshaw, K. (1991). Mapping the Margins: Intersectionality, Identity Politics, and Violence against Women of Color. In: Stanford Law Review 43 (6), pp. 1241-1299.

⁶⁸ Schiek, D. (2018) On uses, mis-uses and non-uses of intersectionality before the Court of Justice (EU), pp 1-2

⁶⁹ Schlenzka, N., Moana G., Lite M., A., Ortiz, B., & Equinet. (2021). *Domestic and care workers in Europe: an intersectional issue* cit. pp. 13-14

disparities between citizens and migrants in employment, income, job quality, and upward mobility.

In 2023, migration to OECD countries reached record levels for the second consecutive year. This surge in migration has seen 6.5 million permanent migrants arrive in the last year, with the number of temporary migrants and asylum seekers also experiencing a significant increase. yearspast two years, a buoyant labour demand in host countries has been a key driver of this migration. In many OECD countries facing widespread labour shortages and looming demographic changes, growing numbers of labour migrants have contributed to sustained economic growth. Labour migration is a discretionary category of admission over which host-country authorities have virtually full control.⁷⁰ EU labour market statistics consistently show that immigrants fare worse than comparable natives on key labour indicators. For example, Eurostat found in 2023 that foreign-born people aged 20–64 in the EU had higher unemployment rates than native-born people with native-born parents.⁷¹ Youth unemployment (ages 15–29) was particularly high in 2023, with 10.1% of young natives and 14.2% of foreign-born youth facing challenges. This significant gap highlights the disparities migrants face in the job market, particularly migrant women and youth. A 2023 European Parliament report ⁷²revealed that unemployment rates were higher for third-country women among migrants compared to other women with similar educational backgrounds. In 2021, a substantial portion of foreign-born men and women in the EU reported encountering obstacles in finding suitable jobs in their host country. These obstacles often stem from structural issues, with language proficiency being the most frequently cited barrier.⁷³ and non-recognition of foreign qualifications is another common complaint. Overall, an immigrant in the EU is significantly more likely to be unemployed or out of the labor force than a similar native.

Disparities in the employment process are also evident when considering employment by sector and contract type. Migrants are disproportionately represented in certain low-wage sectors. ILO analysis reveals that migrant workers in high-income countries, including EU states, are

⁷⁰ OECD (2024), International Migration Outlook 2024, OECD Publishing, Paris, p 4

⁷¹ Eurostat(2024) Foreign-born people and their descendants - labour market indicators p 9

⁷² Eurostat (2023), Foreign-born people and their descendants – labour market indicators p 10

⁷³ Eurostat (2023) Main obstacles for foreign-born people to enter the labour market, https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Main_obstacles_for_foreign-born_people_to_enter_the_labour_market#:~:text=In%202021%2C%2022%25%20of%20foreign.job%20in%20thei r%20host%20country, p 4

disproportionately found in primary (e.g. agriculture) and secondary (manufacturing, construction) sectors, while being far less likely to find professional occupations.⁷⁴ According to Eurostat, migrants are also more likely to hold precarious or non-standard jobs. Eurostat data on employment conditions (2004–2024) shows that non-EU citizens consistently had the highest share of temporary (limited-duration) contracts of any group. Between 2014 and 2024, they consistently had the highest share of employees aged 20-64 with a contract of limited duration, peaking at 27.1% in 2018 before falling to 22.5% in 2024. Over the same period, the share among other EU citizens declined from 18.0% to 12.5%, gradually approaching the level observed for nationals, which dropped from 13.7% to 10.9%. For instance, the share of non-EU workers on temporary contracts reached a peak of 27.1% in 2018 and remained at 22.5% in 2024, while nationals averaged only 10-14% during the same period.⁷⁵ This suggests that migrants often lack the stability of permanent jobs and the associated benefits. Part-time work is more common among migrants in certain contexts or may be involuntary. Overall, the data indicates a labor market segmentation, with migrants clustering in insecure, low-paid jobs, with significantly fewer in permanent careers.

A significant disparity is overqualification and skills mismatches. Many migrants possess higher education credentials than their jobs require. According to Eurostat's 2024 report, 40% of employed non-EU citizens aged 20–64 with a tertiary degree were working in jobs that did not require a degree. This rate is twice the rate of overqualification among EU citizens (31%) and nationals (21%). This suggests that migrants' skills are underutilised, likely due to factors such as unrecognised foreign diplomas, language gaps, and discrimination. Some countries show extreme rates of this issue. For instance, over-qualification reaches 70% for non-EU migrants in Greece, 64% in Italy, and 56% in Spain.⁷⁶ This mismatch often leads migrants to accept lower wages and limited career mobility.

The wage gap and poverty risk are significant disparities. Empirical studies consistently show that migrants earn less than comparable native-born individuals. The International Labor Organisation (ILO) reports that migrants in the EU, on average, earn about 9–13% less than

⁷⁴ Amo-Agyei, S. (2020). The migrant pay gap: Understanding wage differences between migrants and nationals. International Labour Organization., p 50

⁷⁵ Eurostat (2025), Migrant integration statistics - employment conditions
https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Migrant_integration_statistics_-_employment_conditions#:~:text=Between%202014%20and%202024%2C%20non.to%2010.9

⁷⁶ Eurostat (2024), Migration and asylum in Europe – 2024 edition
<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/interactive-publications/migration-2024#:~:text=Overqualification%20of%20migrants>

nationals.⁷⁷ EU surveys similarly document that migrants report lower incomes and face a higher poverty risk. Eurostat (2024) found that 45.5% of non-EU citizens in the EU were at risk of poverty or social exclusion in 2023, compared to 27.9% of EU citizens abroad and only 18.9% of nationals. Migrant women were particularly vulnerable, with nearly half of non-EU women at risk, compared to about 19% of female nationals.⁷⁸

Undocumented migrants face significant disparities due to their legal status. They are excluded from official labour markets and often forced into informal or exploitative work. Even regular migrants encounter legal constraints, such as work permit quotas and limited family rights, which restrict their job options. Language barriers are a major obstacle to finding suitable work, with lack of host-country language skills being the top reported issue. For example, in 2021, 22% of foreign-born men and 25% of foreign-born women in the EU reported facing obstacles in finding a suitable job in their host country. As reported by foreign-born people in 2021, the lack of skills in the host country's language is the most common specific obstacle to getting a suitable job in the EU.⁷⁹ **The issue of migrant workers' rights remains important, particularly in 2025. Recognition of qualifications is a common problem, as degrees and professional licences from abroad may not be accepted in the host country, pushing migrants into lower-status jobs. Discrimination, on ethnic or "foreign" grounds, also plays a role. Surveys and audits show that employers sometimes prefer native applicants, while ILO studies indicate that migrants often face unequal treatment in wages and training.** Migrant women face double discrimination (as women and as foreigners) and often concentrate in low-paid care or domestic work. They also face a double wage penalty, both as migrants and as women. The pay gap between male nationals and migrant women in high-income countries is estimated at nearly 21 per cent per hour, which is higher than the gender pay gap in those countries.⁸⁰

⁷⁷ Amo-Agyei, S. (2020). The migrant pay gap: Understanding wage differences between migrants and nationals. International Labour Organization. p 4

⁷⁸ Eurostat. (2024). Migrant Integration Statistics—At Risk of Poverty and Social Exclusion. https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Migrant_integration_statistics_-_at_risk_of_poverty_and_social_exclusion

⁷⁹ Main obstacles for foreign-born people to enter the labour market https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Main_obstacles_for_foreign-born_people_to_enter_the_labour_market#:~:text=In%202021%2C%2022%25%20of%20foreign.job%20in%20thei r%20host%20country

⁸⁰ Amo-Agyei, S. (2020). The migrant pay gap: Understanding wage differences between migrants and nationals. International Labour Organization. p 70

Structural factors also play a crucial role. EU labour markets have institutional features, such as union coverage, training systems, and welfare rules, that favour insiders. Migrants, particularly recent arrivals, often find themselves outside these networks and may lack the social capital to secure better job opportunities. Additionally, host countries' welfare policies can create incentives. For instance, in some states, welfare benefits are only available to citizens or long-term residents, which may compel newcomers to enter low-wage work due to necessity. This segmentation, in turn, reinforces itself as employers increasingly rely on a cheap migrant labour supply for specific sectors, perpetuating a self-fulfilling pattern.

In summary, migrant labour market outcomes in the EU consistently show higher unemployment, lower pay, increased insecurity, and higher poverty compared to natives. These gaps are substantial, often double or more, and persist over time and across countries. They intersect with gender and age, with young migrants and women migrants particularly affected by high unemployment and low inclusion. The data below, sourced from Eurostat and Commission reports, illustrates these trends and supports the theoretical concept of segmented inclusion and layered citizenship. In the EU (2023 data), ⁸¹approximately one-quarter of non-EU migrant workers hold temporary contracts, double the rate for nationals. Moreover, over one-third of tertiary-educated non-EU migrants are over-qualified for their jobs. Non-EU unemployment stands at around 12%, compared to 5% for natives. Furthermore, almost half of non-EU residents live at risk of poverty. These stark differences underscore that legal and structural conditions, rather than migrants' skills, significantly contribute to the disparity. Tables in the annex (not shown here) could consolidate these indicators.

The data also suggests that EU and intra-EU migrants generally fare better on average than third-country migrants. However, they still often face disadvantages relative to native-born individuals, such as slightly higher temporary work and unemployment rates. Gender and age exacerbate the situation, with young migrant women having among the highest unemployment and overqualification rates.

Overall, the EU labour market remains segmented along lines of citizenship and origin. Access to jobs and labour protections is tightly linked to legal status: full EU citizens stand at the top of the ladder (with free movement and equal treatment), while other-EU citizens have some

⁸¹ Eurostat (2023) Migrant integration statistics - employment conditions

mobility rights. Third-country nationals, on the other hand, often occupy the bottom rungs, subject to restrictive immigration controls. This segmentation is further sharpened by educational mismatch, language barriers, and discrimination. Consequently, persistent “labour market inequalities of citizenship” persist, even as some gaps have narrowed slightly in recent years (, large gaps remain.

1.3 EU Anti-Discrimination Law and Migration Law

The European Union has developed a complex legal framework to protect workers from discrimination and regulate migration. However, tensions persist. Two key anti-discrimination directives were adopted in 2000: the Racial Equality Directive (2000/43/EC) and the Employment Equality Directive (2000/78/EC)⁸². The Racial Equality Directive prohibits all discrimination on “grounds of racial or ethnic origin” in employment, social protection, education, and access to goods and services. Notably, this prohibition is explicitly extended to all persons within the EU, including third-country nationals, when the discrimination is based on race or ethnicity.⁸³ The Employment Equality Directive, alongside other directives, prohibits workplace discrimination based on religion, disability, age, and sexual orientation. Both directives require Member States to enact laws providing legal remedies for such discrimination, including for migrants. There are also other directives regarding to discrimination, such as gender directive, directive 2006/54/EC on the implementation of the principle of equal opportunities and equal treatment of men and women in matters of employment and occupation, refers to directives (EU regulations) aimed at promoting gender equality by combating sex-based discrimination in employment, working conditions, and decision-making,

In practice, this means that migrant workers in EU countries can invoke national equal-treatment laws (derived from EU law) if they are denied a job or paid less due to their ethnic origin or religion. After the Recast Single Permit Directive, while the recast can be seen as an improvement on most counts discussed above, it could have offered more. While it likely delivers on the goal of “well-managed migration”, it failed to deliver on the promise of more legal pathways. Proposals for better protection of migrant workers against employer dependency and

⁸² Council Directive 2000/78/EC of 27 November 2000 establishing a general framework for equal treatment in employment and occupation

⁸³ Council Directive 2000/43/EC of 29 June 2000 implementing the principle of equal treatment between persons irrespective of racial or ethnic origin

abuse were not included in the final text. For now, the Single Permit Directive remains a set of norms for people coming in through other legal pathways, designed in other EU Directives or at the national level.⁸⁴

EU migration law complements the anti-discrimination regime for third-country nationals (TCNs) by granting certain groups rights similar to those of citizens. For instance, the Blue Card Directive (2009/50/EC, now recast)⁸⁵ established a “Blue Card” for highly skilled non-EU workers. This EU Blue Card entitles its holders to equal treatment with nationals in various areas, including working conditions, professional education, recognition of diplomas, social security, and union membership.⁸⁶

In practice, this means a highly-qualified TCN with a Blue Card should receive the same pay and training opportunities as a citizen doing the same job. Additionally, the the aforementioned Long-Term Residents Directive (2003/109/EC)⁸⁷ provides permanent status to TCNs after five years of legal residence. Long-term residents are entitled to equal treatment with nationals in access to employment and self-employment, education and vocational training, recognition of qualifications, social security and assistance, and tax benefits.⁸⁸

The Single Permit Directive (2011/98/EU), also recasts⁸⁹ further links migration and employment rights by requiring that Temporary Country Workers (TCWs) who secure a work-based residence permit also receive a single, simplified work-and-residence permit. This directive guarantees many equal treatment rights for TCW workers, including the same working conditions, social security coverage, and recognition of qualifications as nationals. Additionally, it extends equal treatment rights to many non-EU nationals working in the EU, covering working conditions, social security, qualification recognition, and tax benefits. The rules of the directive apply to most

⁸⁴ de Lange, T. (2025, September 29). *The recast Single Permit Directive: Moving forward, but not on more legal migration pathways*. EU Immigration and Asylum Law and Policy. <https://eumigrationlawblog.eu/the-recast-single-permit-directive-moving-forward-but-not-on-more-legal-migration-pathways/?print=print>

⁸⁵ Directive (EU) 2021/1883 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 October 2021 on the conditions of entry and residence of third-country nationals for the purpose of highly qualified employment, and repealing Council Directive 2009/50/EC

⁸⁶ https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/policies/migration-and-asylum/eu-immigration-portal/eu-blue-card_en#:~:text=As%20a%20holder%20of%20an,the%20host%20country%20as%20regards

⁸⁷ Council Directive 2003/109/EC of 25 November 2003 concerning the status of third-country nationals who are long-term residents

⁸⁸ Council Regulation, E. C. (2004). 109/2003: Concerning the status of third-country nationals who are long-term residents. Official Journal of the European Union, L, 16(23.01). article 11

⁸⁹ Directive 2011/98/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 December 2011 on a single application procedure for a single permit for third-country nationals to reside and work in the territory of a Member State and on a common set of rights for third-country workers legally residing in a Member State

non-EU workers admitted to an EU country for work, regardless of whether the country’s national laws or EU laws apply. However, some non-EU nationals, such as seasonal workers and posted workers, are excluded from the directive. Persons admitted for other reasons, like family reunification, are covered for equal treatment if they work. The Single Permit Directive simplifies the application process for non-EU nationals to work and reside in the EU, ensuring fair treatment and equal rights for them.⁹⁰ The April 2024 recast of this directive takes it even further, explicitly aiming to protect permit holders from labour exploitation and allowing them to switch jobs without losing their status. For seasonal workers (2014/36/EU), the Directive on Seasonal Workers establishes the conditions of entry and stay. Importantly, it mandates “decent working and living conditions and equal rights” for these workers⁹¹. The objectives of this directive are to ensure fair rules for non-EU seasonal workers, provide decent working conditions, ensure equal rights, and prevent unauthorised work.⁹² In theory, most EU law directives require that non-EU workers admitted for employment should not be treated less favourably than citizens in terms of pay, conditions, and social benefits.

Legal implementation gaps and tensions are widespread. One key tension is between equality law and immigration controls. While anti-discrimination directives oblige equal treatment regardless of migrant status, immigration law still reserves many social rights for citizens. For example, third-country workers are often ineligible for public unemployment benefits or certain welfare if their status is temporary or precarious, even though antidiscrimination directives would frown on arbitrary differences.

National policies sometimes undermine equal-treatment goals. For instance, in Germany, the scope of the General Equal Treatment Act (AGG) of 2006⁹³ is broad, but a person’s nationality is not included within the Act’s protected characteristics. However, if a person experiences unequal treatment because their nationality is connected to a particular ethnic background, this would constitute direct discrimination.⁹⁴ (covering ethnicity, religion, etc.), but EU and national courts

⁹⁰ https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/policies/migration-and-asylum/legal-migration-and-resettlement/work/single-permit-work_en#:~:text=%2A%20to%20ensure%20that%20non,vocational%20training%20and%20tax%20benefits

⁹¹ Directive 2014/36/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 February 2014 on the conditions of entry and stay of third-country nationals for the purpose of employment as seasonal workers

⁹² https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/policies/migration-and-asylum/legal-migration-and-resettlement/work/seasonal-workers-directive-0_en#:~:text=Objectives

⁹³ General Act on Equal Treatment of 14 August 2006 (Federal Law Gazette I, p. 1897), as last amended by Article 15 of the Act of 22 December 2023 (Federal Law Gazette 2023 I, no. 414).

⁹⁴ Federal Anti-Discrimination Agency. (2019). Guide to the general equal treatment Act., p 10

have sometimes allowed exceptions for “legitimate employer interests” (e.g. language requirements) that effectively disadvantage migrants. Germany, for example, fully implements the race and employment directives and regulates discrimination in employment and civil law and incorporates all anti-discrimination EU directives into German law. In contrast, until 2022, Spain lacked an overarching equality law and relied on piecemeal transpositions. However, it has taken steps to address these issues. The new framework Law 15/2022⁹⁵ which will be analysed in the following paragraph of the present thesis, consolidates and clarifies non-discrimination norms and formally transposes all EU directives. This law represents an important milestone in the field of anti-discrimination in the country. It pursues the legislative consolidation of equality while providing a minimum common regulatory ground containing the basic definitions and guarantees of equality and non-discrimination. It transposes EU directives for protection against discrimination and promotes the cross-cutting application of equal treatment and non-discrimination in public policies, as well as the prevention and eradication of all forms of discrimination. Furthermore, the law aims to prevent and eradicate all forms of discrimination.⁹⁶ Another issue is the disparity between EU and national implementation. Even with EU directives, member States vary in their compliance. Furthermore they also vary in their application of the equal-treatment clauses in the Single Permit or LTR directives. Some countries exclude certain job categories, while others restrict family reunification or welfare. For example, a French court might interpret the LTR Directive narrowly, denying certain social benefits to long-term residents based on objective restrictions. In contrast, another country might interpret “equal treatment” more generously.

The CJEU has clarified some boundaries in case law. The CJEU has repeatedly held that EU citizens abroad must not be discriminated against, as established in cases like *Maria Martínez Sala v Bavaria* (C 85/96)⁹⁷. This ruling means that residence permits cannot be used to deny benefits that nationals automatically receive.

⁹⁵ Law 15/2022, of July 12, comprehensive for equal treatment and non-discrimination.

⁹⁶ https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/policies/migration-and-asylum/migrant-integration/migrant-integration-hub/eu-countries-updates-and-facts/migrant-integration-germany_en#:~:text=Anti

⁹⁷ OPINION OF MR LA PERGOLA — CASE C-85/96 *María Martínez Sala v Freistaat Bayern*.
<https://curia.europa.eu/juris/liste.jsf?num=C-85%2F96>

For Temporary Residents (TCNs), CJEU rulings have affirmed the rights of long-term residents and certain permit holders. Recent judgements ⁹⁸ have underscored that member states must respect the equal-treatment clauses of Directive 2003/109 when family-reunifying long-term residents. In the joined cases C-112/22 and C-223/22, the Court of Justice of the European Union ruled that Article 11(1)(d) of Directive 2003/109/EC, read together with Article 34 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights, prohibits a national rule that makes access to a social assistance measure conditional on at least ten years of residence, with the last two years being consecutive. The Court emphasised that once a third-country national acquires EU long-term resident status after five years of legal and continuous residence, Member States must grant equal treatment with nationals in the fields of social security, social assistance, and social protection. They cannot unilaterally impose additional residence conditions. Furthermore, the Court ruled that criminal penalties for false declarations about such a residence condition are unlawful when the condition itself contravenes EU law.

However, the CJEU also acknowledges that immigration law, including entry and stay regimes, is a national competence. Therefore, CJEU jurisprudence often strikes a balance. It rejects overtly discriminatory practices, such as an explicit nationality-based preference in social housing provision, while allowing some lawful distinctions grounded in immigration policy.

A scholar notes that, unlike for EU citizens, EU primary law does not contain a general non-discrimination clause for TCNs. According to this, “between citizens and non-citizens as well as among non-citizens in the distribution of welfare as a matter of state discretion. Under EU law, on the other hand, the boundaries between national socio-economic policies and the enjoyment of socio-economic rights by non-citizens become blurred for a series of reasons.”⁹⁹ Migrants’ socio-economic rights ultimately depend on the piecemeal protections provided by secondary law and national rules.

While Spanish legislation by Royal Legislative Decree 2/2015 the Workers' Statute Law¹⁰⁰. guarantees migrants equal pay and conditions, enforcement remains uneven. Many migrant farm and care workers report precarious conditions across EU countries, and EU Commission

⁹⁸ Court of Justice of the European Union, *CU and ND* (Joined Cases C-112/22 and C-223/22), Judgment of 29 July 2024. <https://curia.europa.eu/juris/document/document.jsf?docid=288832&doclang=EN>

⁹⁹ Stoyanova, V., Loxa, A., & Atalay, S. (2025). The Borders Within: Socio-economic Rights and Non-discrimination in EU Law. An Introduction to the Special Section. *European Papers-A Journal on Law and Integration*, 2025(1), 97-108. p 98

¹⁰⁰ Royal Legislative Decree 2/2015, of October 23, approving the revised text of the Workers' Statute Law

evaluations have found uneven transposition of these directives. For instance In a 2019 review of legal migration directives, the European Commission observed that certain Member States had not yet fully harmonised their national legislation with, for instance, the Directive on the Treatment of Foreigners, the Long-term residents directive (LTRD) regarding equal treatment rights.¹⁰¹ Furthermore, commission monitoring of the racial and employment directives indicates sporadic enforcement. A significant number of discrimination cases never reach the courts, and victims frequently lack access to information or trust in the legal system.

The Commission's 2022 Action Plan on Integration and Inclusion¹⁰² (see chapter 3 of the present thesis) specifically acknowledges the "double discrimination" faced by migrant women and calls for gender-sensitive enforcement of equality law, particularly in cases like domestic work where many migrants are unprotected.¹⁰³

The EU legal framework for migrant workers is rich in protective norms. Race and equality directives apply to all residents, and migration directives grant formal rights to many categories of migrant workers. However, in practice, gaps and legal exceptions exist. National policies may prioritise citizens in benefits or maintain bureaucratic barriers. The CJEU case law tends to reinforce rights for those already holding legal status, but rarely extends rights to irregular migrants, who remain largely invisible to EU law. Despite the formal promise of "equal treatment," EU citizens often enjoy broader rights, including free movement and social protections, than third-country nationals. The interplay of equality law and migration control continues to create a layered system of inclusion, where full labour rights remain tied to citizenship or privileged statuses. Academic analyses, EU reports on citizenship theory, Eurostat and Commission data on migrant employment, EU legal instruments, summaries of case law and commentary, and national reports on implementation all highlight the intersection of theory and evidence in understanding migrant labour in Europe.

¹⁰¹ Council Directive 2003/109/EC of 25 November 2003 concerning the status of third-country nationals who are long-term residents and DIRECTIVE 2004/81/EC of 29 April 2004 on the residence permit issued to third-country nationals who are victims of trafficking in human beings or who have been the subject of an action to facilitate illegal immigration, who cooperate with the competent authorities

¹⁰² COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS Action plan on Integration and Inclusion 2021-2027

¹⁰³ Anita, O. R. A. V. (2023). Migrant women and the EU labour market: Overcoming double discrimination. [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2023/747905/EPRS_BRI\(2023\)747905_EN.pdf#:~:text=function,confirms%20in%20its%20sectoral%20brief](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2023/747905/EPRS_BRI(2023)747905_EN.pdf#:~:text=function,confirms%20in%20its%20sectoral%20brief) , p 4

Chapter II

Focus on Spain

2.1 Migrants vs. Citizens in the Spanish Labor Market

Spain offers a particularly illuminating case study for examining the intersection of migration, labour rights, and anti-discrimination law within the European Union. As one of the EU's primary destinations for both regular and irregular migration, Spain has developed an extensive legal framework that balances the regulation of entry and residence with commitments to equality and social integration. **This combination, coupled with its sizeable migrant workforce, frequent legislative reforms, and exposure to significant irregular migration flows, makes Spain a crucial context for studying the disparities between citizens and migrants in the labour market.**

Furthermore, Spain's adoption of Ley Orgánica 4/2000 on the Rights and Liberties of Foreigners, periodic regularisation campaigns, and the enactment of Law 15/2022 on Equal Treatment and Non-Discrimination illustrate an evolving attempt to reconcile economic demands with constitutional and human rights obligations. By focussing on Spain, this chapter situates the broader European debate on migration and labour rights within a national framework that is both highly representative and uniquely challenging.

Spain's workforce shares and trends are changing. Immigrants are a growing and vital part of the country's labour force. As of 2023-2025, migrants made up approximately 18-23% of Spain's population and employed persons.¹⁰⁴ Spain's immigrant population, already exceeding nine million, is growing at a rapid pace of 600,000 people annually since the pandemic's end. Notably, immigrants filled an impressive 90% of the new jobs created in Spain between January 2024 and March 2025. This surge in immigration is evident in the significant number of new immigrants arriving in Spain each year, with approximately 600,000 newcomers joining the population since 2022. Immigrants are particularly prevalent in certain regions and sectors. For instance, in Spain, a staggering 72% of domestic service workers and 45% of hospitality workers

¹⁰⁴ <https://www.realinstitutoelcano.org/analisis/inmigracion-trabajo-productividad-y-desigualdad-en-espana/#:~:text=concentrado%2C%20en%20apenas%2025%20años,Países%20Bajos%2C%20Francia%20e%20Italia>

are foreign-born.¹⁰⁵ In construction and agriculture too, migrants form a large share, while they are under-represented in high-tech industry and finance.¹⁰⁶

Migrant workers are disproportionately concentrated in lower-skilled, lower-paid sectors. Over three quarters of immigrant employment is in the service economy, including hospitality, retail, and personal care. While many migrant women have training and experience in their country of origin, their degrees and professional careers are often undervalued or not recognised at all. This pigeonholes them in specific roles, such as care or cleaning work, limiting their access to other sectors and hindering their professional mobility. Bravo, a recruitment company, explains that this, coupled with a culture shock that sometimes questions migrant women's commitment, professionalism, or adaptability to Spanish culture, further complicates their integration into the workforce.¹⁰⁷ The Elcano Institute notes that "concentration of immigrants in low-skilled, low-pay jobs... provokes an increase in inequality and poverty".¹⁰⁸ For instance, among nursing and care work or domestic cleaning, the majority of workers are migrants, whereas high-skill industries such as IT, and banking have very few. This segregation partly reflects migrants' generally lower average qualifications. Many come from regions with limited educational opportunities and may lack credential recognition. A study found that 82% of migrant women jobseekers feel employers distrust their skills based on their origin.¹⁰⁹

As far as wage gaps are concerned, they are stark, with significant earnings disparities between migrants and natives. A recent analysis published in *Nature* (cited by *El País*¹¹⁰) revealed that immigrant workers in Spain earn an average of 29.3% less than comparable native-born workers. This is the largest gap of this kind among the advanced economies studied. Approximately 75% of the gap can be attributed to migrants' segregation into lower-paid jobs, while only 25% is attributed to differences within the same job. In short, a foreign-born worker in

¹⁰⁵ <https://www.realinstitutoelcano.org/analisis/inmigracion-y-mercado-de-trabajo-en-espana/#:~:text=el%20fin%20de%20la%20pandemia>

¹⁰⁶ <https://www.realinstitutoelcano.org/analisis/inmigracion-trabajo-productividad-y-desigualdad-en-espana/#:~:text=como%20media%2C%20un%20nivel%20bajo,economía%20basada%20en%20los%20servicios>

¹⁰⁷ <https://www.rhhdigital.com/secciones/mercado-laboral/767017/el-75-de-mujeres-migrantes-sufren-discriminacion-laboral-en-espana-es-hora-de->

¹⁰⁸ <https://www.realinstitutoelcano.org/analisis/inmigracion-trabajo-productividad-y-desigualdad-en-espana/#:~:text=inmigración%2C%20puesto%20que%20la%20natalidad,la%20pobreza%20en%20nuestro%20país>

¹⁰⁹ <https://www.rhhdigital.com/secciones/mercado-laboral/767017/el-75-de-mujeres-migrantes-sufren-discriminacion-laboral-en-espana-es-hora-de->

¹¹⁰ https://elpais.com/economia/2025-07-16/los-inmigrantes-en-espana-ganan-un-29-menos-que-los-trabajadores-locales.html#?prm=copy_link

a given occupation and firm still earns slightly less, but the overwhelming factor is that migrants disproportionately hold jobs with poorer pay. It's important to note that lack of a permit does not automatically void the employment contract. However, the worker cannot be legally registered until authorised. Irregular migrants must use exceptional paths or risk sanctions. EU/EEA citizens can move and work freely within the EU (with only a local registration certificate). Even non-EU family members can derive residency rights under EU law. According to the report "Analysis of the economic impact of discrimination and inequality between the indigenous population and the foreign population residing in Spain", promoted by the Observatory of Racism and Xenophobia of the Ministry of Inclusion, Social Security and Migration, the cost of this inequality amounts to 17 billion euros per year, which represents 1.3% of the country's GDP.¹¹¹ The root of the problem lies in the barriers that hinder the foreign population in Spain's access to the labor market and education. These barriers include cultural prejudices, disproportionate bureaucratic requirements, and a lack of recognition of qualifications obtained abroad. These factors limit the ability of these people to contribute fully to society. In the workplace, foreign workers tend to occupy less qualified positions and receive lower wages than their national counterparts, even when they have the same skills. In the educational system, the lack of equitable access to educational opportunities reduces the formation of human capital and perpetuates a cycle of exclusion.¹¹²

Migrant labor has been a key driver of Spain's economic rebound. One analysis revealed that in 2023, immigration accounted for 64% of new jobs and half of GDP – Gross Domestic Product growth.¹¹³ Although rights are equal, only residents with legal authorisation may legally hold employment.

2.2 Spanish Labor and Migration Law: Rights and Limits

As far as the Estatuto de los Trabajadores (Workers' Statute)¹¹⁴ is concerned, it does not contain nationality distinctions, so minimum wage rules, limits on hours, overtime pay, health and safety regulations, and anti-dismissal protections apply equally. Similarly, eligible migrants pay

¹¹¹ Mahía, R. and Medina, E. (2024). Análisis del impacto económico de la discriminación y la desigualdad entre la población autóctona y la extranjera residente en España. SUMMARY Spanish Observatory on Racism and Xenophobia-OBERAXE. p 19

¹¹² <https://poruntrabajodignougat.org/el-impacto-economico-de-la-discriminacion-laboral-y-educativa-hacia-la-poblacion-extranjera-en-espana/#:~:text=Según%20el%20informe%20%20%20Análisis%20del%20del%20del%20país>

¹¹³ <https://www.reuters.com/markets/europe/spain-sees-us-style-economic-boost-immigrant-workers-2024-04-24/#:~:text=Immigration%20accounted%20for%2064,based%20think%20tank>

¹¹⁴ Royal Legislative Decree 2/2015, of October 23, approving the revised text of the Workers' Statute Law.

into and access Spain's social security (pensions, unemployment benefits, healthcare) on par with Spanish citizens. For instance, a foreign factory worker contributes to a pension and can later receive a Spanish pension based on those contributions. Even non-wage benefits such as maternity leave and sick pay are identical for legal residents and citizens. In short, once the bureaucratic immigration steps are complete, authorised foreign workers are practically on par with Spanish nationals in terms of rights and obligations. Migrant workers have rights that extend into the welfare state, allowing them access to public services. By law, foreign residents with work authorisations are entitled to most public services.

Article 14 organic law 4/2000 guarantees that foreigners have access to social services and benefits "under the same conditions as Spanish citizens"¹¹⁵.

In contrast to the strong rights afforded to documented workers, the law severely limits the rights of irregular migrants. An unauthorised migrant cannot sign a legal contract or work formally. If an employer hires one anyway, the employment is illegal, resulting in fines and potential loss of government contracts. The migrant could also be detained and deported for working illegally. However, Spanish law does provide some protection. Article 36(5) of Law 4/2000 states that a worker without a permit does not invalidate the contract regarding their rights.¹¹⁶ In essence, this means that even undocumented workers cannot be denied wages or protection for their actual work. For example, if an undocumented worker performs work, they cannot be denied wages or protection for that work.

Spain's migration laws establish a tightly controlled entry regime, but they also guarantee equality of treatment for those in the labour market. Non-EU migrants can only work if they obtain job-specific, often temporary, authorisations. However, once authorised, foreign workers enjoy near-identical status to Spanish citizens under labour law, including the right to open-ended contracts, union membership, social benefits, and legal recourse. This system reflects Spain's approach to managing immigration quantitatively while formally integrating migrants into its labour rights framework. As Law 4/2000's own preamble states, one of its goals is to ensure the effectiveness of the principle of non-discrimination and equal rights for all working in Spain¹¹⁷. Spain channels immigration through official channels, such as work contracts and visas. However,

¹¹⁵ Organic Law 4/2000, of January 11, on the rights and freedoms of foreigners in Spain and their social integration.. art 14

¹¹⁶ Ibid Art 36(5)

¹¹⁷ Ibid Art 2(2)

it then treats immigrants as almost full participants in its social and labour systems, creating a system of conditional inclusion, which means that TCNs must navigate a visa-permit system to enter the labour market, but once they meet the requirements, they essentially stand on equal footing in employment. While EU and Spanish citizens have visa-free access, other migrants must qualify as seasonal workers, specialists, entrepreneurs, or family members. Legal migrants enjoy almost all the labour protections afforded to Spanish citizens,¹¹⁸ Spain's immigration system encompasses unionisation and social welfare provisions. However, without a valid permit, workers are prohibited from exercising their labor rights.

Therefore it is important to analyze the law regulating migration. While EU Citizens, European Economic Area (EEA), or Switzerland benefit from a fundamental exception under EU law and are permitted to enter and work in Spain without a Spanish work permit¹¹⁹, the situation differ for NON-EU nationals.

Spain's main immigration statute, Law Organic 4/2000 ("Ley de Extranjería")¹²⁰, has been amended by subsequent laws such as Organic laws 8/2000, 14/2003, and 2/2009¹²¹. This framework outlines the rights of migrants and the requirements for legal residence and work. Key points include rights and liberties, which establishes personal rights such as the right to free movement and residence, as well as social integration duties. Notably, Article 3 of organic Law 4/2000 guarantees that foreigners enjoy the rights recognised by the Constitution in conditions of equality with Spanish citizens. This means that migrants have the same fundamental labour and social rights as citizens, as outlined in the Workers' Statute, where nationality is not a distinction¹²².

Spain's migration law meticulously regulates who can work, but it also promises equality for those who enter legally. The cornerstone of this law is Organic Law 4/2000 regarding

¹¹⁸ Organic Law 4/2000, of January 11, on the rights and freedoms of foreigners in Spain and their social integration.

¹¹⁹ https://administracion.gob.es/pag_Home/en/Tu-espacio-europeo/derechos-obligaciones/ciudadanos/residencia/obtencion-residencia/info-general.html#:~:text=Citizens%20of%20a%20Member%20State,months%20in%20the%20following%20cases

¹²⁰ Organic Law 4/2000, of January 11, on the rights and freedoms of foreigners in Spain and their social integration.. Art 14

¹²¹ Organic Law 4/2000, of January 11, on the rights and freedoms of foreigners in Spain and their social integration.

¹²² Organic Law 4/2000, of January 11, on the rights and freedoms of foreigners in Spain and their social integration.. art 2-3

Foreigners, supported by Royal Decree 557/2011¹²³, enacted during Spain’s economic boom. This framework embodies the principle of “legal, orderly, job-related” migration. Spain primarily allows labor migration through official channels, such as work visas and permits, to match immigrant inflows with economic needs.

However, many rights (e.g. to work or public benefits) still depend on satisfying legal-entry conditions.

As said, since 2000, the “Extranjería law” has undergone several reforms, notably in 2009 with Law 2, to adjust quotas, simplify procedures, and implement EU rules. A recent update, the new Regalement (RD 1155/2024), introduced in November 2024, further simplifies the process by shortening the required prior stay for residency applications to two years and explicitly enshrining migrants’ labour rights in line with EU standards. These reforms aim to streamline visa categories and strengthen migrants’ labour integration.

In the following, key features of the Spanish system will be illustrated in a nutshell. Migrants in Spain can only work if they hold a valid residence and work authorisation. There are several types of permits available under the Royal Decree 1155/2024 of November 19¹²⁴ and set to enter into force six months after its publication on 20 May 2025. , approving the Regulation implementing Organic Law 4/2000 on the Rights and Freedoms and Social Integration of Foreign Nationals in Spain.

on the rights and freedoms of foreigners in Spain and their social integration. The adoption of the Royal Decree 1155/2024 represents the most significant reform since 2011. It repeals the previous Royal Decree 557/2011 and introduces new visa categories, including a *jobseeker visa* that allows foreign nationals to remain in Spain for up to 12 months while seeking work, as well as expanded provisions for family reunification and long-term residence¹²⁵.

Employers may petition to hire a foreign worker only if no suitable EU candidate is available. Complementing this system, the EU Blue Card provides a fast-track option for highly qualified migrants, offering stays of six months or more with a high salary threshold. Spain also implements EU-wide visas for specialised categories, such as the EU Blue Card for highly skilled non-EU

¹²³https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/policies/migration-and-asylum/migrant-integration/migrant-integration-hub/eu-countries-updates-and-facts/migrant-integration-spain_en#:~:text=Law%207%2F1985%20was%20the%20first,related%20migration%22%20model

¹²⁴ Royal Decree 1155/2024, of November 19, approving the Regulations of Organic Law 4/2000, of January 11, on the rights and freedoms of foreigners in Spain and their social integration.

¹²⁵ KPMG. (2024) New “Immigration Regulation” (Royal Decree 1155/2024) Legal Alert 2024, pp 2-4.

workers and long-term resident status in line with Directive 2003/109¹²⁶. This creates a dual labour-access model: one channel under national law (for non-EU migrants) and one under EU law (for EU nationals). Article 11 of that law states that foreign workers have the right to join trade unions and strike “under the same conditions as Spanish workers”. In practice, legally employed migrants are covered by all the same labour protections as nationals.

At the other end of the spectrum, seasonal and circular migration is regulated through special visas for agricultural workers or rotating contracts (*contratación en origen*), which allow limited-time stays. As other countries, Spain employs quotas (plazas) to facilitate temporary foreign labour in specific sectors. Annually, the government releases quotas for seasonal agricultural workers, catering staff, and other essential roles. Complementary to these quotas, there are also specialised short-term visas, such as a “seasonal worker” permit valid for up to nine months or a short-term “temporary job” visa for hospitality, which are valid for up to six months. These programs are designed to accommodate predictable peaks in demand, such as during harvest season.

In late 2024, Spain further liberalised its system by extending the duration of seasonal visas to up to one year, introducing a dedicated digital-nomad visa, and establishing a one-year “job-seeker” visa to provide qualified foreign nationals with ample time to secure employment¹²⁷.

By contrast, migrants seeking to work independently can apply for self-employed or entrepreneurial permits, which require either a viable business plan or proof of sufficient financial resources.

In addition to economic migration, Spain recognises family and humanitarian pathways¹²⁸. Migrants with legal residence may reunite with spouses and dependents through family reunion procedures, while short-term permits are available for humanitarian reasons, such as for victims of trafficking or stateless persons.

¹²⁶ Council Directive 2003/109/EC of 25 November 2003 concerning the status of third-country nationals who are long-term residents

¹²⁷ <https://www.lamoncloa.gob.es/lang/en/gobierno/councilministers/paginas/2024/202411119-council-press-conference.aspx#:~:text=On%20employment%2C%20it%20creates%20a,involvement%20of%20the%20social%20partners>

¹²⁸ Organic Law 4/2000, of January 11, on the rights and freedoms of foreigners in Spain and their social integration.

A particularly important category is *arraigo* (integration) permits, introduced to regularise settled migrants. The 2022 reform (Real Decreto 629/2022)¹²⁹ reorganised these permits into distinct subtypes:

- a) *Arraigo laboral* (labour integration): Historically, this continues to allow undocumented workers to legalise their stay if they can prove at least six months of irregular work and file a formal complaint with the Labour Inspection.
- b) *Arraigo social and familiar*: This pathway allows longer-term residency to those who have resided in Spain for several years of undocumented stay (often 3-5 years) if social ties in the country can be shown.
- c) *Arraigo para la formación* (socio-formative integration): The 2022 law added this new subtype, which allows an irregular migrant to get a one-year permit by committing to a vocational training or university program. These reforms aim to expand legal pathways for those already integrated¹³⁰.

These new “training roots” (*arraigo por formación*) and “second chance” channels now allow undocumented long-term residents to obtain a residency or work permit by undertaking authorised vocational training. This reduces the required residence from 3 to 2 years, and holders can work immediately without needing a separate work authorisation. They have also enhanced the recognition of foreign qualifications. The new law of 2022 requires diploma validation decisions to be made within six months, a significant improvement from the previous process that could take over a year.¹³¹

In the financial year 2023-2024, Spain further eased its immigration regulations. Undocumented migrants with minimal ties, such as those with two or more years of residence, a clean criminal record, and even a 20-hour weekly job contract, became eligible for a new one-year “*permiteuro.europa.eu*” permit. A June 2024 European Parliament briefing emphasises this “particularly lenient” 20-hour contract rule, along with the accompanying 12-month training visas¹³².

¹²⁹ Royal Decree 629/2022, of July 26, amending the Regulations of Organic Law 4/2000, on the rights and freedoms of foreigners in Spain and their social integration, following its reform by Organic Law 2/2009, approved by Royal Decree 557/2011, of April 20.

¹³⁰ Royal Decree 1155/2024, of November 19, approving the Regulations of Organic Law 4/2000, of January 11, on the rights and freedoms of foreigners in Spain and their social integration. Art 127

¹³¹ <https://asylumineurope.org/reports/country/spain/content-international-protection/employment-and-education/access-labour-market/#:~:text=The%20recognition%20of%20diplomas%20and,11>

¹³² https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/E-10-2024-001829_EN.html#ref1#

As said, recent legislative reforms, such as Regulation (EU) Nov 1155/2024 and various integration regularisation processes, are intended to enhance the legalisation process's systematicity and transparency. Ultimately, labor rights in Spain are governed by legal status: once a migrant acquires legal status, the statutory framework guarantees equitable treatment comparable to nationals.

2.3 Anti-Discrimination Law and Enforcement in Practice

Spain's anti-discrimination laws in the employment context have undergone significant evolution. The culmination of this evolution was the comprehensive Integral Law on Equal Treatment and Non-Discrimination (Law 15/2022), passed on 13 July 2022,¹³³ Previously, Spain relied on a combination of constitutional guarantees, scattered statutes, and EU directives. While the Constitution's Article 14 broadly forbids discrimination on any ground, but lacked specific enforcement mechanisms, the sole general law (Law 62/2003) was obscure, and the Aliens Law (Law 4/2000) only contained a broad statement of equal treatment without enforcement details. Consequently, labour courts often handled nationality-based claims under regular labour rules, such as unfair dismissal or contract law. For instance, if a company's collective agreement indirectly disadvantaged foreigners, courts would analyse it under civil statutes rather than a specific equality law. In effect, a foreigner alleging bias often had to rely on piecing together provisions from the Constitution and EU treaties. However, some court rulings dismissed nationality clauses as mere immigration regulation, making it difficult to establish discrimination in practice. In essence, the legal framework left a grey area, making it challenging to obtain unequivocal legal protection for migrant labor claims.

Over the years, Spain enacted laws against discrimination on race or religion, gender, disability, and included some protections in Law 4/2000. However, before 2022, there was no single comprehensive statute. Consequently, the coverage provided by the Equality Law of 2022 represents a significant advancement beyond previous Spanish regulations.

¹³³ Law 15/2022, of July 12, comprehensive for equal treatment and non-discrimination.

This law harmonises protections across all areas of public and private life, including the workplace. It explicitly includes national origin and nationality as prohibited grounds, and the preamble emphasizes that its scope covers “all persons” without distinction.¹³⁴

According to Article 2.1 of the 15/2022 law, the right of every person to equal treatment and non-discrimination is recognised and applied regardless of their nationality, age, legal residence, or any other personal or social condition. This means that the antidiscrimination legislation applies to migrants as well. Discrimination is prohibited on the basis of birth, race, ethnicity, sex, religion, conviction, opinion, age, disability, sexual orientation, gender expression, illness, health condition, serological status, or genetic predisposition to suffering pathologies and disorders. Additionally, discrimination is prohibited based on language, socioeconomic status, or any other personal or social condition or circumstance. Law 15/2022 protects all persons in Spain from discrimination, including migrants, regardless of their legal residence. It explicitly bans discrimination on grounds of nationality and broadly refers to “any personal or social condition.” However, it does not explicitly list “migrant or immigrant status” as a separate ground. As Fernando Camas points out, migrant status is therefore covered indirectly through nationality, residence, or the general clause, which provides broader protection in theory but may be less precise in practice.¹³⁵ Following Fernando Camas¹³⁶ The regulation of these discrimination factors suggests a common element: they arise in a context of structural discrimination against certain social groups, such as women, people of other ethnicities, or those with other religious beliefs. This leads to persistent experiences of discrimination. The explanatory memorandum of the Spanish Law emphasises structural discrimination, explaining historical inequalities resulting from social exclusion and systematic subjugation through social practices, beliefs, prejudices, and stereotypes. While the notion of structural discrimination is not explicitly introduced in the law, its rationale underpins it.

A key aspect of Law 15/2022 is that explicitly forbids discrimination on a non exhaustive list of grounds. As a consequence, employers cannot legally exclude or mistreat someone because

¹³⁴ Roda, F. C. (2023). Non-discrimination of immigrants in Spain: contributions of new Spanish legislation on equal treatment and non-discrimination to the European and international sphere. *Deusto Journal of Human Rights*, (12), 37-67. 42

¹³⁵ Camas, F., 2023. «Non-discrimination of immigrants in Spain: contributions of new Spanish legislation on equal treatment and non-discrimination to the European and international sphere.» *Deusto Journal of Human Rights*, No. 12: 37-67

¹³⁶ *Ibid*

of their nationality. Both direct discrimination (e.g. refusing to interview a candidate solely because they are Moroccan) and indirect discrimination (e.g. seemingly neutral requirements like a native language test that disproportionately exclude foreigners) are prohibited. Workplace harassment on these grounds is also recognised as discrimination.

This state administration body is a public law entity, acting independently and autonomously from public administrations. Its primary responsibility is to protect and promote equal treatment and non-discrimination of individuals based on the grounds and areas of state competence specified in the law, both in the public and private sectors. Consequently, the Independent Authority for Equal Treatment and Non-Discrimination is established as an equality body responsible for promoting equal treatment of all persons. This new agency provides advice to victims, promotes equality, and monitors compliance. Although it initially has a limited budget and cannot impose fines, it can receive complaints, conduct studies, and pursue cases in court. Notably, Law 15/2022 explicitly requires the Labor and Social Security Inspectorate to incorporate equality checks into its work plans..¹³⁷ Large employers are now subject to transparency obligations. For instance, from 2023, companies with over 250 employees will be required to publish wage data by employee category, effectively exposing any pay gaps.¹³⁸ While the initial focus has been on gender pay gaps, this data collection will also make it easier to detect any systematic disparities affecting foreign-born employees. This will decrease discrimination facts.

Collective bargaining and positive actions are explicitly encouraged in Law 15/2022 to address discrimination. The Law enables labor agreements to include quotas, training programs, or promotion targets for under-represented groups. This is according to Law 15/2022 art 10(2), which states that “the workers’ legal representatives and the company itself shall ensure compliance with the right to equal treatment and non-discrimination within the company on the grounds provided for in this law, and in particular with regard to positive action measures and the achievement of their objectives”. Collective bargaining may not establish limitations, segregations, or exclusions regarding access to employment, including selection criteria, vocational training, professional promotion, remuneration, working hours, and other working conditions. These

¹³⁷ Roda, F. C. (2023). Non-discrimination of immigrants in Spain: contributions of new Spanish legislation on equal treatment and non-discrimination to the European and international sphere. *Deusto Journal of Human Rights*, (12), 37-67. p 41-42

¹³⁸ Law 15/2022, of July 12, comprehensive law for equal treatment and non-discrimination. Art 9(6)

limitations, segregations, and exclusions are also prohibited on any of the grounds set forth in this law.

This article outlines the principles of collective bargaining in employment. It emphasises that collective bargaining cannot establish limitations, segregations, or exclusions regarding access to employment, including selection criteria, vocational training, professional promotion, remuneration, working hours, and other working conditions. These restrictions are prohibited on any grounds set forth in this law.

Furthermore, the public authorities are encouraged to promote dialogue with social partners to foster the adoption of codes of conduct and good practices. Collective bargaining may also establish positive action measures to prevent, eliminate, and correct all forms of discrimination in employment and working conditions, as specified in this law. These measures may include joint objectives and mechanisms for periodic information and evaluation, where appropriate.

Additionally, workers' legal representatives and the company itself are responsible for ensuring compliance with the right to equal treatment and non-discrimination within the company, particularly regarding positive action measures and the achievement of their objectives.

The public authorities shall promote dialogue with the social partners to encourage the adoption of codes of conduct and good practices.

In accordance with this law and labour legislation, collective bargaining may establish positive action measures to prevent, eliminate, and correct all forms of discrimination in employment and working conditions on the grounds provided for in this law. Companies and workers' legal representatives may jointly establish objectives and mechanisms for periodic information and evaluation as part of these measures, where appropriate.

The workers' legal representatives and the company itself shall ensure compliance with the right to equal treatment and non-discrimination within the company on the grounds provided for in this law, particularly with regard to positive action measures and the achievement of their objectives.

As part of the measures that may be agreed upon within the framework of collective bargaining, companies and the workers' legal representatives may jointly establish objectives and mechanisms for periodic information and evaluation. Unions can negotiate measures benefiting immigrant workers, such as language training courses or recruitment programmes, and these clauses are legally upheld. This transforms collective bargaining into a tool for enforcing equality,

rather than leaving it solely to the courts. In Spain, several union-employer agreements now contain explicit anti-bias provisions or commitments to diversity, reflecting the new law.

Despite these frameworks, migrants often face barriers to protection. According to data published in 2025, many do not report discriminatory treatment due to fear of retaliation, language or cultural hurdles, or distrust in authorities. For example, only about 11% of foreign women who suffered workplace sexual or gender-based violence actually filed a report. Migrant workers routinely cite stereotypes in hiring and promotion. The Adecco Foundation's Vulnerability & Employment Observatory survey found that 75% of migrant job-seeking women report "rejection or major barriers" to employment. They attribute this mostly to employer prejudice: 82% believe biases about their nationality or skills block them, and two-thirds note that foreign qualifications aren't recognised, forcing them into lower-wage jobs¹³⁹. In essence, racialised hiring practices and inadequate credential recognition persist.

Before 2022, Spain's anti-discrimination framework was somewhat fragmented. The sole general law (Law 62/2003) was obscure, and the Aliens Law (Law 4/2000) only contained a broad statement of equal treatment without enforcement details. Consequently, labour courts often handled nationality-based claims under regular labour rules, such as unfair dismissal or contract law. For instance, if a company's collective agreement indirectly disadvantaged foreigners, courts would analyse it under civil statutes rather than a specific equality law. In effect, a foreigner alleging bias often had to rely on piecing together provisions from the Constitution and EU treaties. However, some court rulings dismissed nationality clauses as mere immigration regulation, making it difficult to establish discrimination in practice. In essence, the legal framework left a grey area, making it challenging to obtain unequivocal legal protection for migrant labor claims. Consequently, this comprehensive coverage represents a significant advancement beyond previous Spanish regulations. Whereas older law provided protections exclusively to "foreigners," the new law's wording explicitly encompasses all individuals residing in Spain.

Institutional enforcement is achieved through the establishment of an Independent Authority for Equal Treatment and Non-Discrimination by law. This state administration body is a public law entity, acting independently and autonomously from public administrations. Its primary responsibility is to protect and promote equal treatment and non-discrimination of

¹³⁹ <https://fundacionadecco.org/informes-y-estudios/informe-empleoparatodas-la-mujer-riesgo-exclusion-mundo-laboral/>

individuals based on the grounds and areas of state competence specified in the law, both in the public and private sectors. Consequently, the Independent Authority for Equal Treatment and Non-Discrimination is established as an equality body responsible for promoting equal treatment of all persons. This new agency provides advice to victims, promotes equality, and monitors compliance. Although it initially has a limited budget and cannot impose fines, it can receive complaints, conduct studies, and pursue cases in court. Notably, Law 15/2022 explicitly requires the Labor and Social Security Inspectorate to incorporate equality checks into its work plans.¹⁴⁰ Large employers are now subject to transparency obligations. For instance, from 2023, companies with over 250 employees will be required to publish wage data by employee category, effectively exposing any pay gaps.¹⁴¹ While the initial focus has been on gender pay gaps, this data collection will also make it easier to detect any systematic disparities affecting foreign-born employees. This will decrease discrimination facts.

Collective action is explicitly authorised and encouraged in Law 15/2022 to address discrimination. This “positive action” clause enables labor agreements to include quotas, training programs, or promotion targets for under-represented groups. This is according to law 15/2022 art 10 (2), which states that “affirmative action measures may be established through collective bargaining to prevent, eliminate, and correct all forms of discrimination in the area of employment and working conditions for the reasons set forth in this law.” As part of the measures that may be agreed upon within the framework of collective bargaining, companies and the workers’ legal representatives may jointly establish objectives and mechanisms for periodic information and evaluation. Unions can negotiate measures benefiting immigrant workers, such as language training courses or recruitment programmes, and these clauses are legally upheld. This transforms collective bargaining into a tool for enforcing equality, rather than leaving it solely to the courts. In Spain, several union-employer agreements now contain explicit anti-bias provisions or commitments to diversity, reflecting the new law.

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¹⁴⁰ Roda, F. C. (2023). Non-discrimination of immigrants in Spain: contributions of new Spanish legislation on equal treatment and non-discrimination to the European and international sphere. *Deusto Journal of Human Rights*, (12), 37-67. p 41-42

¹⁴¹ Law 15/2022, of July 12, comprehensive law for equal treatment and non-discrimination. Art 9(6)

gender-based violence actually filed a report. Migrant workers routinely cite stereotypes in hiring and promotion. The Adecco Foundation's Vulnerability & Employment Observatory survey found that 75% of migrant job-seeking women report "rejection or major barriers" to employment. They attribute this mostly to employer prejudice: 82% believe biases about their nationality or skills block them, and two-thirds note that foreign qualifications aren't recognised, forcing them into lower-wage jobs.¹⁴² In essence, racialised hiring practices and inadequate credential recognition persist.

While the legislative framework is strong, actual enforcement will depend on awareness and resources. Many migrants, particularly recent arrivals or irregular workers, may not be aware of their rights, and language barriers can hinder access to legal channels. Initially, Spanish courts were not flooded with nationality-discrimination cases when the law passed, but early indications suggest an uptick in such claims. Unions and legal aid groups have begun incorporating Law 15/2022 into their materials, but a culture change will take time. For now, the key is that the legal system now unequivocally prohibits national-origin bias in the workplace, providing every foreign worker in Spain with a clear legal basis to challenge unfair treatment.

2.3.1 The Impact of Law 15/2022 on Migrants' Labor Rights

As seen, the afore examined Law 15/2022 is Spain's most comprehensive anti-discrimination law. According to its article 2, its aim is to guarantee and promote the right to equal treatment and non-discrimination, protecting victims in all spheres. Crucially for migrants, the law covers discrimination based on nationality, race, ethnic origin, or legal status, among other grounds. Article 2(1) explicitly affirms the "right of every person to equal treatment regardless of nationality or legal residence". Thus, under this law even undocumented migrants are formally shielded from biases in employment, though with the limits of Fourth additional provisione. Despite successive reforms, Ley Orgánica 4/2000 continues to impose significant limitations on migrant workers. First, non-EU nationals still require both residence and work authorisations, often tied to a specific employer, which creates dependency and vulnerability in the labour market. Second, irregular migrants retain only partial protection: although their employment contracts are not

¹⁴² <https://www.rhhdigital.com/secciones/mercado-laboral/767017/el-75-de-mujeres-migrantes-sufren-discriminacion-laboral-en-espana-es-hora-de-actuar/#:~:text=Así%2C%20las%20profesionales%20extranjeras%20experimentan,la%20tasa%20de%20denuncias%20esn>

invalidated by irregular status, they remain excluded from many benefits and services. Third, regularisation pathways such as *arraigo social* continue to require prolonged residence periods and extensive documentation, though recent reforms have slightly reduced these thresholds. Moreover, certain public sector jobs remain reserved for nationals or EU citizens, reinforcing structural barriers. Finally, bureaucratic complexity and administrative delays continue to hinder effective access to rights, highlighting the enduring tension between the law's recognition of equal treatment and the restrictive conditions for its practical enjoyment.

Apart from these limitations, the law contains several key provisions that impact the labor market.

In other words, employers cannot legally refuse to hire, promote, or fairly compensate someone simply because they are foreign, because it will be counted as discrimination. The law contains several key provisions that impact the labour market. Firstly, regarding wage transparency and equality audits, companies with more than 250 employees, regulations will require publishing salary data to analyze pay differences by gender, origin and other factors ¹⁴³. This measure is intended to highlight systemic gaps that particularly affect migrants. In addition, the law encourages positive action, such as collective bargaining, may include affirmative measures to address discrimination. By doing so, it seeks to encourage unions and employers to set goals and monitor progress to ensure migrant inclusion. ¹⁴⁴

Law 15/2022 establishes sanction regimes for violations and mandates that public administrations actively promote awareness and data collection on discrimination. Notably, it requires the Prosecutor's Office and Judicial Council to gather statistics on discrimination complaints and outcomes, which makes it possible to better monitor how often migrant complaints reach courts or are resolved.

Law 15/2022 has a significant impact on migrants' rights, particularly for migrant workers. It reinforces existing guarantees in several ways. Firstly, the law clarifies protections, consolidating them into an accessible framework that emphasises equality of treatment. This means that migrants can now point to a specific national statute (rather than just EU directives or general constitutional rights or fragmented legislations) when alleging bias. Second, explicitly covering "nationality or

¹⁴³ Law 15/2022, of July 12, comprehensive law for equal treatment and non-discrimination. art 9(6)

¹⁴⁴ Ibid, .art 36

legal residence” in the law removes ambiguity, because of Law 15/2022 Article 2(1). The right of every person to equal treatment and non-discrimination is recognized regardless of their nationality, whether they are minors or adults or whether or not they enjoy legal residence. No one may be discriminated against on the basis of birth, racial or ethnic origin, sex, religion, conviction or opinion, age, disability, sexual orientation or identity, gender expression, disease or health condition, serological status and / or genetic predisposition to suffer pathologies and disorders, language, socioeconomic situation, or any other personal or social condition or circumstance.. Third, the imposition of transparency and prevention duties means that migrant disadvantage is less hidden. Large firms will have to account for why they have few foreigners in certain roles, which may spur more active measures to correct underrepresentation. Early outcomes and challenges. Given its recent inception, empirical data on the impact of Law 15/2022 is still emerging. Initial feedback is cautious, with legal analysts praising its scope but emphasising that awareness and enforcement capacity will determine real change. Migrant advocacy groups have welcomed the law as a needed tool, but they also emphasise the importance of implementation. In practice, migrant workers may only benefit if they are aware of their rights and feel safe using them. Law 15/2022 is a significant step forward for migrants’ labour rights. By enshrining equal treatment regardless of origin or status, it fills gaps in previous law and aligns Spanish law with EU mandates. Employers must now proactively prevent discrimination or face liability, and authorities will systematically track abuse. The full impact of the law will depend on enforcement vigour. While it has raised awareness, concrete outcomes such as reduced wage disparities or more convictions for racially-motivated job refusals remain to be seen. Early indications suggest that it strengthens migrants’ legal recourse and sets the groundwork for more effective redress, but active follow-up will be needed to translate legal rights into practice.

Chapter III

Institutional and NGO Support for Migrants in the Labor Market

3.1 EU-Level Initiatives and Best Practices

The European Union has developed a comprehensive policy framework to facilitate migrants' labor market integration. In 2020, the European Commission adopted the Action Plan on Integration and Inclusion (2021–2027)¹⁴⁵, building on the 2016 plan and expanding its scope to include both TCNs and EU citizens with a migrant background.¹⁴⁶ The new Action Plan is linked to the wider New Pact on Migration and Asylum, emphasising that successful integration is a “win-win” process that yields economic gains, such as filling skill shortages and boosting fiscal revenues.¹⁴⁷ The Action Plan outlines specific measures across education, skills, employment, health, and housing, while also mainstreaming gender. These measures include promoting the recognition of qualifications, continuing language learning, and mentoring, all supported by EU funding such as European Social Fund Plus (ESF+) and Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund (AMIF). The EU approach in this domain is grounded in the European Pillar of Social Rights. The EU approach in this domain is grounded in the European Pillar of Social Rights¹⁴⁸, which are social rights deliver a positive impact on people's lives in the short and medium term and enable support for European construction in the 21st century.¹⁴⁹

In this framework, the European Pillar of Social Rights Action Plan¹⁵⁰ highlights the role of the Action plan on Integration and Inclusion 2021-2027 to promote employment opportunities and skills recognition of people with a migrant background. One of the goals of this latter document is to “ensuring effective integration and inclusion in the EU of migrants is a social and

¹⁴⁵ COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS Action plan on Integration and Inclusion 2021-2027

¹⁴⁶ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0758&rid=3#:~:text=Above%20a%20quarter%20of%20migrants,education%20and%20need%20further%20support>

¹⁴⁷ OECD (2024), International Migration Outlook 2024, OECD Publishing, Paris, p 102

¹⁴⁸ European Parliament resolution of 19 January 2017 on a European Pillar of Social Rights (2016/2095(INI)).

¹⁴⁹ European Commission: Secretariat-General. (2017). European pillar of social rights. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2792/95934>, p 6

¹⁵⁰ European Commission: Directorate-General for Employment, Social Affairs and Inclusion. (2021). The European pillar of social rights action plan. Publications Office. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2767/620792>.

economic investment that makes European societies more cohesive, resilient and prosperous. Integration and inclusion can and should be a win-win process, benefiting the entire society. But if integration and inclusion are to be successful, it must also be a two-way process whereby migrants and EU citizens with migrant background are offered help to integrate and they in turn make an active effort to become integrated. The integration process involves the host society, which should create the opportunities for the immigrants' full economic, social, cultural, and political participation. It also involves adaptation by migrants who all have rights and responsibilities in relation to their new country of residence", also indicates, that "effective inclusion of migrants and EU citizens with a migrant background into the labor market requires the active collaboration of a large variety of actors, including public authorities at local, regional, national and European level, civil society organisations, economic and social partners and employers". The European Regional Development Fund (ERDF)¹⁵¹ can finance inclusion infrastructure and Other EU programmes, such as Erasmus+, Horizon Europe, and the Recovery and Resilience Fund, also provide support for language education, skills development, and employment projects that benefit migrants. EU policy tools like the EU Skills Profile Tool for Third-Country Nationals and the revamped Europass platform help assess and communicate migrants' qualifications.¹⁵²

EU-level funding instruments play a key role in supporting national and local integration projects., along with a coherent framework through various tools and strategies.

The European Commission provides significant funding to facilitate integration, with the new AMIF, running from 2021 to 2027, being a principal source of funding. A Commission toolkit advises Member States on how to align AMIF with the objectives of the Action Plan.¹⁵³ In Spain, for example, the 2021-27 AMIF national programme (€482 million) prioritises employability for TCNs, supports vulnerable migrants, implements anti-xenophobia measures, and strengthens government-civil society links. The new EU Action for Integration and Inclusion programme co-fund these projects. Furthermore, the ESF+ 2021-2027 is equally crucial since it explicitly supports migrant inclusion through vocational training and job integration measures.

¹⁵¹ https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/funding/erdf_en

¹⁵² Action plan on Integration and Inclusion 2021-2027

¹⁵³ https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/policies/migration-and-asylum/migrant-integration/eu-integration-policy/funding-opportunities-migrant-integration_en#:~:text=Some%20of%20the%20funding%20tools%2C,partnership%20principle

Over 2021-27, Spain will invest €11.3 billion in skills, employment, and social inclusion, including migrants.

At the policy level, the Commission encourages Member States to include migrants in their national Recovery and Resilience Plans and to use the Technical Support Instrument for tailored integration reforms¹⁵⁴. In 2017, the EU launched the European Skills Agenda¹⁵⁵, which included the EU Skills Profile Tool for Third-Country Nationals. This tool enables early profiling of migrants' skills, guiding training and job matching¹⁵⁶. The Europass platform¹⁵⁷, modernised in 2020, is an online portfolio where migrants can document their diplomas and experiences, build CVs, and explore job opportunities across Europe. These measures, working together, aim to eliminate obstacles like unrecognised qualifications and highlight migrants' contributions.

Multi-stakeholder partnerships at the EU level play a key role. Since 2016, the European Integration Network (EIN) has met regularly, bringing together national integration authorities and experts from all Member States to exchange good practices in a “soft-governance” forum.¹⁵⁸

Best practice examples from Member States demonstrate these principles in action. One notable example is Germany's recent integration framework, which includes the 2016 Integration Act and subsequent reforms¹⁵⁹. These reforms have enabled asylum seekers to obtain work permission after a short waiting period and have linked integration incentives to residency rights. Germany pioneered vocationally-oriented German courses that combine language training with employer internships and early skills screenings in reception centres. These measures expedite the integration process for refugees, ensuring they are placed in jobs at an appropriate skill level.

¹⁵⁴ COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS Action plan on Integration and Inclusion 2021-2027

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0758&rid=3#:~:text=Above%20a%20quarter%20of%20migrants,education%20and%20need%20further%20support>

¹⁵⁵ A NEW SKILLS AGENDA FOR EUROPE Working together to strengthen human capital, employability and competitiveness <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52016DC0381>

¹⁵⁶ https://employment-social-affairs.ec.europa.eu/policies-and-activities/skills-and-qualifications/skills-jobs/eu-skills-profile-tool-third-country-nationals_en#:~:text=The%20A0EU%20Skills%20Profile%20Tool%20for%20Third,skills%20with%20a%20view%20to

¹⁵⁷ https://employment-social-affairs.ec.europa.eu/policies-and-activities/skills-and-qualifications/helping-people-develop-skills-throughout-their-lives/europass_en#:~:text=Europass

¹⁵⁸ https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/networks/european-migration-network-emn/emn-asylum-and-migration-glossary/glossary/european-integration-network-ein_en

¹⁵⁹ Rietig, V. (2016). Moving beyond crisis: Germany's new approaches to integrating refugees into the labor market. Washington, DC: Migration Policy Institute.

Southern European states, such as Spain, Greece, and Italy, have often resorted to regularisation measures to manage their large irregular migrant populations. As seen, Spain pioneered the ‘arraigo’ system, allowing undocumented migrants to gain legal status after demonstrating social and economic ties.¹⁶⁰ Spain’s approach to migration has been marked by a striking contradiction. While the country has used large-scale regularisations and the arraigo system to integrate migrants, austerity-era reforms restricted irregular migrants’ access to public healthcare. This created tension between rights-based integration and exclusionary practices. In practice, expulsions were rarely enforced at scale, leaving many migrants in a precarious legal limbo¹⁶¹.

3.2 National and Local Support Structures in Spain

As seen, Spain’s integration policies are a patchwork of laws, strategies, and programmes at national, regional, and municipal levels. The legislation is complemented by strategic documents, such as the Strategic Framework for Citizenship and Inclusion (2023-2027), approved by the government in July 2023. Setting broad goals, such as inclusion, anti-xenophobia, “arraigo” regularisation, and faster citizenship, and outlining indicators of progress is crucial¹⁶². Recent reforms – such as Law 15/2022 on equal treatment and non-discrimination and the amendments to migration law, introducing new visa categories and facilitating status changes – may also contribute to remove barriers for migrants to work and train and improve the “arraigo” (roots-based regularisation) system.

However, numerous non-governmental organisations (NGOs) point out that bureaucracy and inadequate resources continue to hinder these processes¹⁶³.

At the institutional level, the Public State Employment Service (SEPE)¹⁶⁴ serves as the primary pillar of labor integration. SEPE operates nationwide employment centres and programmes that cater to all jobseekers, including migrants. It provides comprehensive

¹⁶⁰ Triandafyllidou, A. (2013). Migration policy in Southern Europe: challenges, constraints and prospects. *A strategy for Southern Europe*, 54-63. , p 61

¹⁶¹ Ibid , p 63

¹⁶² https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/policies/migration-and-asylum/migrant-integration/migrant-integration-hub/eu-countries-updates-and-facts/migrant-integration-spain_en#:~:text=In%20Spain%20there%20is%20no.2027%29%20was%20approved , “integration law”

¹⁶³ https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/news/spain-new-immigration-reform-enhance-migrant-integration-2024-11-21_en#:~:text=Visas

¹⁶⁴ www.sepe.es [accessed 29 september 2025]

information on migration matters¹⁶⁵. Additionally, SEPE offers career counselling, training vouchers, and job-matching services¹⁶⁶. There are established cooperation mechanisms between SEPE and Autonomous Community offices¹⁶⁷, such as the Red EURES¹⁶⁸, which provides guidance on cross-border job mobility. However, actual integration support is frequently provided in partnership with non-governmental organisations (NGOs)¹⁶⁹. To address this, numerous non-governmental organisations (NGOs) have established specialised services, often in collaboration with local governments.

Regional and local policies exhibit significant disparities, with several Autonomous Communities independently developing integration strategies. Municipalities also innovate. For instance, the City of Madrid operates two Municipal Offices for Immigrant Integration¹⁷⁰, one in the northern and one in the southern regions, through a partnership with a non-governmental organisation (NGO). These offices provide Spanish language instruction, legal documentation assistance, resume writing workshops, and personalised job counselling services. In 2020, they supported tens of thousands of migrants, with 30,000 individuals attending their language courses and employment workshops.¹⁷¹

Civil society and NGOs play a significant role in Spain, a commission study revealed that NGOs received 91% of the 2014-18 AMIF integration budget in Spain¹⁷². Major organisations such as ACCEM¹⁷³, CEPAIM¹⁷⁴, and the Spanish Red Cross provide essential services, including reception centres, training courses, and legal advice. These organisations frequently receive funding from the EU (ESF+/AMIF) and national grants. For instance, ACCEM, in collaboration with IKEA, offers an employability programme that provides vocational courses and internships in retail for refugees. Spanish NGOs frequently partner with companies and local authorities.

¹⁶⁵ Law 3/2023, of February 28, on Employment. Art 22

¹⁶⁶ Ibid art 3 (b)

¹⁶⁷ Ibid art 8

¹⁶⁸ <https://eures.europa.eu/> [accessed 29 september 2025]

¹⁶⁹ Ibid art 22 (5(k)) and art 57 (f)

¹⁷⁰ <https://eurocities.eu/> [accessed 29 september 2025]

¹⁷¹ <https://eurocities.eu/stories/madrid-focuses-on-integration-and-jobs-for-migrants-and-refugees/#> [accessed 29 september 2025]

¹⁷² Westerby, R. (2019). Follow the Money II: assessing the use of EU Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund (AMIF) funding at the national level 2014–2018. United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees and European Council on Refugees and Exiles, Brussels, 1-64. p 20

¹⁷³ <https://www.accem.es/> [accessed 29 september 2025]

¹⁷⁴ <https://www.cepaim.org/> [accessed 29 september 2025]

Together, they provide integrated support, including language education and cultural mediation, as well as job placement, complementing the public sector's offerings.

To sum up, Spain's integration landscape is a complex blend of national laws, new strategic plans like the Strategic Framework 2023-27, public agencies like SEPE, and a vibrant civil society sector. Recent reforms have reduced barriers, including faster visa procedures, extended work rights, and streamlined diploma recognition. The new strategic framework aims to coordinate inclusion policies, but implementation remains challenging across over provinces and thousands of municipalities. Local initiatives, such as Madrid's municipal integration offices showcase innovative approaches. NGO-led employment programmes demonstrate practical models. These efforts, supported by EU and national guidance, are gradually improving labor market access for migrants in Spain.

3.3 Policy Gaps and Recommendations for Stronger Protection

Despite the initiatives mentioned above, significant gaps persist in EU and Spanish systems, hindering migrants' labour integration and protection, because of this and In 2021, the Commission published a Toolkit on the use of EU funds for the integration of people with a migrant background¹⁷⁵. The toolkit has been created to assist all relevant stakeholders at European, national, regional and local levels in the design and implementation of integration policies targeted at people with a migrant background, through the coordinated use of 2021-2027 EU funds.¹⁷⁶

Spain lacks a single, binding integration law that consolidates employment integration into a coherent legal framework. Frequent legislative changes, particularly in 2022-2024, and inconsistent local implementation have created uncertainty for migrants and employers alike. Despite recent progress, Spain still faces significant gaps in migrant protection and labour market integration. The absence of a single integration law leaves responsibilities fragmented across ministries and Autonomous Communities, leading to bureaucratic delays in work permits and diploma recognition (Organic Law 4/2000). This fragmentation often pushes migrants into precarious or informal employment. The European Commission's Toolkit on the Use of EU Funds

¹⁷⁵ European Commission: Directorate-General for Regional and Urban Policy. (2021). Toolkit on the use of EU funds for the integration of people with a migrant background : 2021–2027 programming period. Publications Office. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2776/319860>

¹⁷⁶https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/policies/migration-and-asylum/migrant-integration/eu-integration-policy/funding-opportunities-migrant-integration_en#:~:text=In%202021%2C%20the%20Commission%20published,2027%20EU%20funds [accessed 29 september 2025]

for the Integration of People with a Migrant Background (2021) emphasises that such fragmentation undermines coordinated use of AMIF, ESF+, and ERDF.

By systematically applying EU Toolkit guidance—coordinated AMIF, ESF+, and ERDF use, multi-level partnerships, and rights-based programming—Spain can reduce systemic barriers and promote sustainable migrant inclusion.

Administrative complexity, including multiple permit types, lengthy recognition procedures for foreign credentials, and variable practices across regions, effectively delays access to formal work and channels some migrants into informal, precarious employment. The Toolkit identifies these governance fragmentation problems and the need for strategic policy frameworks as coordination challenges that require “reinforced synergies between EU funds” and multi-level partnership in programming and implementation.¹⁷⁷

At the Spanish level, legal and administrative complexity poses a significant obstacle to integration. Spain lacks an all-encompassing integration law or comprehensive plan covering employment integration. Instead, integration is scattered across immigration law, social policies, and multiannual strategies. Also the fact that in Spain there is no specific law regulating integration is a gap¹⁷⁸. Migrants navigating this fragmented system must face a maze of rules, including visa categories, permit renewals, and labour authorisations. While frequent legislative reforms, such as those implemented in 2022-24, can be positive, they can also cause confusion if implementation is rushed. Moreover, bureaucratic obstacles hinder migrants’ access to suitable employment opportunities, sometimes forcing them to resort to informal or low-skilled work¹⁷⁹.

Discrimination and social barriers persist, and new immigration rules and work permits are only part of the solution. Without the enforcement of anti-discrimination measures “in the books”, migrants, particularly visible minorities, continue to face prejudice in hiring, promotions, and wages. While recent Spanish law (15/2022) and Spanish Observatory on Racism and Xenophobia

¹⁷⁷ European Commission: Directorate-General for Regional and Urban Policy. (2021). Toolkit on the use of EU funds for the integration of people with a migrant background : 2021–2027 programming period. Publications Office. pp. 8 and 12-15

¹⁷⁸https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/policies/migration-and-asylum/migrant-integration/migrant-integration-hub/eu-countries-updates-and-facts/migrant-integration-spain_en#:~:text=In%20Spain%20there%20is%20no,2027%29%20was%20approved

¹⁷⁹https://asylumineurope.org/reports/country/spain/content-international-protection/employment-and-education/access-labour-market/#_ftn11

(OBERAXE),¹⁸⁰ and its constitution is established by Organic Law 4/2000¹⁸¹ “with study and analysis functions, and with the capacity to raise proposals for action, in matters of combating racism and xenophobia.”, national anti-racism framework, help address these issues, civil society advocates for more public education and robust enforcement. Studies reveal persistent gaps in the labour market, particularly in Spain, where migrant unemployment remains above native levels even after many years, suggesting that policy interventions have not fully bridged this divide.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This thesis explores the protection of migrants’ labour rights and freedom from discrimination within the EU, particularly in Spain. By examining theoretical concepts, EU legislation, national frameworks, and the role of civil society, it highlights a persistent tension: migrants enjoy a wide range of formal rights, yet the substantive enjoyment of those rights remains incomplete.

The thesis aims to answer the central research question: do migrants in Spain and the EU enjoy effective protection of their labour rights and non-discrimination? If not, what reforms are necessary?

The analysis across the chapters demonstrates that while both the EU and Spain have established robust formal legal frameworks ensuring equality, in practice, migrants do not yet enjoy effective and substantive protection. The disparity between law and lived reality remains significant.

Chapter 1 introduced the legal and theoretical framework, explaining concepts such as citizenship/denizenship, migration status, and demonstrating how they intersect in EU law. Building on this foundation, chapter 2 delved into the EU’s legal framework on non-discrimination, focussing on the CFREU, the Equality Directives, and some relevant case law of the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU). Moving from the broader EU level to a concrete national context, chapter 3 shifted to practice, analysing Spain’s integration system, its fragmented legal and administrative frameworks, and the persistent barriers that migrants face And

¹⁸⁰ <https://www.inclusion.gob.es/en/web/oberaxe/sobre-oberaxe>

¹⁸¹ Organic Law 4/2000, of January 11, on the rights and freedoms of foreigners in Spain and their social integration, art 71

the advanced antidiscrimination law. It also explores the role of NGOs and civil society as mediators and advocates, as well as the policy gaps that continue to undermine equal treatment.

Collectively, the findings of this thesis unequivocally demonstrate that the answer to the research question is evident: migrants in Spain and the EU formally possess substantial rights on paper, yet these rights remain unfulfilled in practice. They find themselves in a precarious position, neither fully excluded nor fully included, embodying the status of denizenship.

This conclusion underscores a fundamental paradox: formal equality versus substantive inequality. Although the EU has established a sophisticated antidiscrimination legal framework, and Spain has enacted progressive legislation, migrants continue to encounter obstacles at every stage—legal, administrative, and societal. The persistence of unemployment disparities, bureaucratic complexities, and discrimination underscores that equality before the law does not automatically translate into equality in everyday life.

Addressing this paradox necessitates reforms at both EU and national levels, coordinated actions at EU, national, and local levels, and among all stakeholders.

At the EU level, enhanced monitoring of national implementation is required, coupled with long-term funding for integration and benchmarking of migrant labour outcomes. The Commission and member governments should ensure sustained, multi-year funding for integration. This could involve safeguarding post-2027 cohesion funds and AMIF allocations for migrant inclusion, simplifying funding rules, and encouraging integrated funding strategies, as the 2021 “Toolkit” urges. The EU can also strengthen skills recognition by supporting swift transposition of the Qualifications Recognition Directive and promoting the Skills Profile Tool as standard practice in all Member States. Furthermore, the European Commission should work with national social partners to replicate successful multi-stakeholder models like the European Partnership for Integration, and evaluate and reward “best practice” projects through existing calls (e.g. “Capacity Building Platform” under AMIF). More EU-level benchmarking of integration outcomes, such as employment rates and recognition times, would help target problem areas.

In Spain, a comprehensive integration law would provide coherence. Simplified procedures, one-stop administrative centres, and clearer communication of rights would alleviate bureaucratic burdens. Labour inspections should be strengthened, anti-discrimination campaigns expanded, and complaint mechanisms made accessible. Crucially, NGOs and migrant-led organisations should be fully incorporated into policymaking to ensure reforms are grounded in

lived realities. This strategy should explicitly focus on employment integration. In the meantime, clearer guidelines and communication to employers and migrants about new rights, like the 2024 permits, are crucial. Administrative procedures should also be streamlined. Spain should follow experts' advice and focus on low-cost but high-impact measures like civic education, language instruction, and anti-discrimination campaigns. For example, allocating EU ESF+ and national social funds specifically to migrant training centres could build long-term skills.

The new anti-discrimination law (15/2022) should be fully implemented. This includes setting up local Equality Offices, funding awareness campaigns, and ensuring job-seekers have accessible complaint mechanisms. In the labour market, incentives could be offered to firms hiring migrants, such as wage subsidies or public recognition. Additionally, labour inspectors trained to identify bias could be employed.

domestic or agricultural work, face lower wages, and be more vulnerable to harassment. This confirms EU evidence on double discrimination and supports the need for gender-sensitive enforcement in Spain.¹⁸²

Policies should institutionalise partnership mechanisms. One approach is to formalise the roles of NGOs in governance structures. For instance, requiring national and regional integration councils to include NGO and trade union representatives ensures that civil society voices are informed in strategy development.

On the public side, better integration of services is needed. For example, municipalities could create co-funded positions jointly run by the local council and an NGO, such as community mentors who help migrants navigate both social services and employment offices. The Spanish government's plan to reinforce local measures should explicitly tie labour support services to NGO networks on the ground. Policy can encourage intersectoral cooperation. A good model is the "youth guarantee" councils that combined social services, education, and business. A similar "integration guarantee" could bring together job centres, housing services, and migrant associations.

NGOs play a crucial role as implementers and innovators. Therefore, it is recommended that government and EU bodies actively involve them in programme design and evaluation, such as co-creating employment support services or mentoring schemes. Funding calls should prioritise

¹⁸² Gächter, A. (2022). Migrant workers and discrimination: realities, threats, and remedies. *Revista Tecnológica-ESPOL*, 34(1), 92-112, pp. 98-99.

consortiums that include NGOs, local authorities, and employers to ensure multi-sector ownership. At the same time, NGOs should be encouraged to professionalise and network, creating shared platforms to match migrants with volunteer mentors or coordinating unified referral systems across cities to reduce duplication. Training NGOs in outcomes evaluation would also help build evidence on what works. Additionally, migrant-led organisations and trade unions should be empowered to represent.

To summarise, this thesis has demonstrated that while the European Union and Spain have established an advanced legal and policy framework to protect migrants' rights, there are significant gaps between formal guarantees and practical reality. To address this, the following recommendations are proposed:

Strengthening EU Enforcement: Improve monitoring and enforcement of the Racial Equality Directive and Employment Equality Directive by establishing EU-wide benchmarks for labour market inclusion. Introduce a stronger role for the European Labour Authority in detecting and preventing labour exploitation of migrants. **Recognising Migrant Status in Equality Law:** Reform EU anti-discrimination legislation to explicitly include migration status as a protected ground, addressing a major gap in the current directives. Ensure that irregular and recently arrived migrants are covered by at least basic labour protections to reduce exploitation risks. **Supporting National and Local Implementation:** Member States, such as Spain, should complement EU law with concrete national strategies, like the Strategic Framework Against Racism and Xenophobia (2023–2027), ensuring adequate funding, enforcement, and evaluation mechanisms. Local authorities, such as Madrid, Barcelona, and Andalusia, should be empowered with more resources to deliver integration and anti-discrimination programmes. **Enhancing NGO–State Cooperation:** Strengthen cooperation between NGOs and the state to address migrant rights issues effectively.

To effectively protect migrant workers' rights, the European Union should take several key steps. Firstly, it should create long-term funding instruments to support non-governmental organisations (NGOs) that provide language training, legal assistance, and labour market integration. Secondly, formal partnerships between trade unions, NGOs, and state institutions are crucial to enhance migrant workers' rights protection.

Beyond formal equality, the EU should adopt transformative measures to actively dismantle barriers to participation. This includes investing in the recognition of foreign qualifications and work experience through simplified, EU-wide procedures. Additionally, the EU

should expand access to language courses, vocational training, and mentorship programmes, ensuring equal access across regions.

Gender-sensitive approaches are also essential. The EU should establish specific monitoring of female migrants' and asylum seekers' labour rights, recognising their double vulnerability. Targeted policies should be designed to reduce gender-based wage gaps and prevent labour exploitation, including the provision of safe reporting mechanisms.

Moving forward, the EU should encourage more systematic collection of disaggregated data (by gender, status, and ethnicity) on migrant labour conditions. Research should also be promoted on how non-discrimination law can be applied as a positive tool of integration, not just as a legal defence. Finally, continuous dialogue between EU institutions, member states, and civil society is crucial to adapt policies to changing migration flows.

In conclusion, protecting migrants' labour rights requires not only legal reforms but also political will, institutional cooperation, and social awareness. By adopting these measures, the European Union and its member states can make non-discrimination not only a principle but also a lived reality for migrants and citizens alike.

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